

Modelling the influence of weather and climate in human disease: salmonellosis today and tomorrow

by

Laura C. González Villeta

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Department of Comparative Biomedical Sciences,
School of Veterinary Medicine
Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences
University of Surrey

Supervisors:

Dr Giovanni Lo Iacono

Dr Joaquín Prada

Prof Alasdair Cook

Prof Gordon Nichols

Dr Jessica Wu

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“(...) scrutinizing and deducting from the details of reality in order to pursue something which we can't see directly but can follow the traces of. In the awareness that we can always be wrong, and therefore ready at any moment to change direction if a new track appears; but knowing also that if we are good enough we will get it right and will find what we are seeking.” (Rovelli, 2016)

Summary

The significance of the environment within the *One Health* approach for addressing emerging health challenges is gaining widespread recognition. The observed seasonal pattern in the incidence of certain infectious diseases, such as salmonellosis, prompted to investigate weather as a potential driver of cases and to question its ability to predict incidence. *Salmonella* is an important causative agent of diarrhoeal disease worldwide with an estimated 80.3 million cases annually. In Europe, *Salmonella* is frequently involved in foodborne outbreaks, accounting for almost one in three foodborne outbreaks. This thesis investigates the main meteorological factors associated with human salmonellosis and characterized their role in contributing to disease. The overarching objective of the thesis is to improve preparedness of salmonellosis informed from meteorological data.

The conditional incidence model is a statistical approach to estimate the incidence of salmonellosis based on weather conditions by stratifying 17 years of historical data from England and Wales. One of the novelties of this method lies in the comprehensive exploration of the effect of 13 weather factors with high spatial-temporal linkage and stratified in different combinations. The robustness of the methodology was validated by comparing the model outcomes with reported laboratory-confirmed data, as well as its application in a different location (*i.e.*, the Netherlands). The model was also applied to investigate the impact of eggs and chicken on disease occurrence under different temperatures, and to assess the effect of climate change on the seasonality of salmonellosis.

Air temperature ($>10^{\circ}\text{C}$), relative humidity, precipitation (dry conditions), dewpoint temperature ($7-10^{\circ}\text{C}$), and day length (12-15h) were identified as key weather factors associated with salmonellosis, irrespective of geographical location. In a future climate scenario marked by rising temperatures, this conditional incidence suggests an increase in the overall number of cases with a less marked seasonal pattern. The presented research expands our understanding of the widely accepted but under-investigated role of weather and climate in modulating disease. Additionally, this thesis contributes to generating hypotheses on the mechanisms through which weather contributes to disease, establishing a foundation for future predictive tools applicable to other environmentally-driven diseases.

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Abbreviations

APHA	Animal and Plant Health Agency
CFU	Colony-forming units
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Control
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EGR	Exponential growth rate
EU	European Union
GIS	Geographic Information System
GNN	General Neural Network
IDW	Inverse Distance Weighted interpolation
LSOA	Layer Super Output Area
MEDMI	MetOffice Medical and Environmental Data Mash-up Infrastructure
NTS	Non-typhoidal <i>Salmonella</i>
PHE	Public Health England
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
RH	Relative Humidity
SE	<i>Salmonella</i> Enteritidis
SIR	Susceptible-Infectious-Recovered model
ST	<i>Salmonella</i> Typhimurium
T	Temperature
Tmax	Maximum air temperature
UK	United Kingdom
UKCP	UK Climate Projections
UKHSA	UK Health Security Agency, former PHE
UV	Ultraviolet
WHO	World Health Organization

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Research question and scope of this thesis

According to the latest United Nations projections, the world's population is now more than three times larger than it was in 1950 and is expected to reach 10.4 billion in 2100 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022). Population growth implies an increased anthropogenic impact on the environment and ecosystems, such as habitat degradation, closer interaction with wildlife and climate change. These challenges present an imminent risk for the emergence of new and re-emerging diseases, emphasizing the need to study environmental and weather factors as key components to address future pandemics through a *One Health* approach.

The association between disease and weather dates back to Hippocrates (460-378 BC), who wrote about a common link between disease and the environment: air, water quality and season of the year (Jones, 1868). This conception has been consolidated by technological advances that enabled high-resolution weather forecasts and electronic records, facilitating the development of predictive models. From the patterns observed in salmonellosis notifications in the past 29 years in England and Wales, a peak is systematically observed in late summer (Figure 1-1). This led to the main research question: **what is the role of weather and climate in the incidence of salmonellosis disease?** Weather and climate have a different influence on salmonellosis. While weather refers to the conditions of the atmosphere over a short period of time (*i.e.*, weeks and months), climate is the cumulative result of weather over longer periods of time (usually years or decades).

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Figure 1-1. Salmonellosis cases reported per week in England and Wales for the years 1989-2020 by UKHSA. An annual seasonal pattern is observed, as well as a steady downward trend in cases from 1998.

Multiple interacting factors are involved in the seasonality of diseases, often entailing a time lag. The increase of salmonellosis cases appears to be associated with higher temperatures, albeit other environmental factors could be involved. The exact contribution of each weather factor as well as its relative impact on the disease is not well known. Modelling is applied in this context to provide a better and detailed understanding on the role of weather as modulator of salmonellosis disease and how it relates to higher bacterial counts in food. I will go back in the available incidence data to the estimated day of infection and identify the weather conditions related to the increases in cases and hypothesise about the causes.

In principle, modelling the drivers of infection would be an appropriate approach, as infection is a precursor of disease. However, this thesis exclusively focuses on the analysis of laboratory-confirmed symptomatic cases, that is, disease events. Therefore, laboratory-diagnosed disease will be used as a proxy for infection. While many studies exploring the relationship between weather and disease tend to focus on temperature and relative humidity –two essential physical requirements for microbial growth–, this thesis takes a more comprehensive approach. It evaluates a wide range of relevant weather factors and characterises the simultaneous effect of multiple factors on the incidence of salmonellosis. Additionally, it assesses the effect of temperature on relevant food sources associated with the disease.

In terms of future scenarios, the WHO states that an increase in temperature or duration of high-temperature episodes may promote greater multiplication of *Salmonella* in foodstuff (WHO, 2018). More specifically, EFSA has estimated an increase of about 20,000 cases of salmonellosis over the next decade in Europe (EFSA, 2020). The model developed in this thesis is used to better understand the impact of climate change on the incidence and distribution of salmonellosis cases, including their specific seasonal patterns.

Salmonella enterica was chosen for this research due to its significant social and economic impact, as outbreaks continue to occur despite preventive measures being implemented. In addition to this, the availability of large amount of data collected over many years made it an ideal choice. The high-resolution nature of the data played an instrumental role in building the model and drawing robust conclusions. While the analysis is limited to human data due to restricted access to animal data, it is acknowledged that efforts to integrate both types of data are of great interest.

1.2 Aim and objectives

The importance of the study lies in the fact that diseases are dynamic processes that require extensive knowledge to control. Understanding disease-specific seasonal patterns is important in designing and improving intervention strategies. The aim of this research is to contribute to the understanding of the role of weather and climate in seasonal and spatio-temporal fluctuations in the incidence of salmonellosis in humans. To achieve this, the following objectives were set:

- **Reviewed existing knowledge** on non-typhoidal salmonellosis in humans, sources of infection, the effect of weather and climate influencing microbial growth and disease incidence, as well as common approaches used to model this relationship (Chapter 2).
- **Identified relevant weather factors** and their interconnected influence on the number of salmonellosis cases reported in England and Wales (Chapter 5). A statistical model was developed to assess the influence of weather in driving salmonellosis cases.
- **Explored the universality of the effect of weather** on salmonellosis, regardless of the geographical location (Chapter 6). The statistical model was applied to the incidence

data from a different country from the one in which it was originally developed (*i.e.*, the Netherlands).

- Estimated the **impact that climate change** may have on the patterns of salmonellosis incidence in the near future (2043) in England and Wales (Chapter 7).
- Investigated the **effect of temperature on the growth of *Salmonella* in the main foodstuffs** associated with salmonellosis and the relevance it has on the overall incidence in humans (Chapter 8). A mechanistic approach was used for this. The reader can jump to this chapter after Chapter 3 for a detailed focus on the link between the microbial growth process of *Salmonella* and the observed epidemiological data.

Chapter 3 presents the general principles of the methodology followed in the different chapters identifying the effect of weather. The particular adaptations of the methodology for each case are specified in the relevant chapters. And, lastly, Chapter 4 outlines an epidemiological description of the incidence data from England and Wales used to build the model.

Chapter 2

Literature review

2.1 *Salmonella* as a foodborne source of disease

Foodborne diseases entail both a public health and economic burden for society, with non-typhoidal *Salmonella* (NTS) being one of the most widely distributed foodborne agents of disease in humans. NTS comprises *S. enterica* serovars other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*. *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* are the predominant serovars involved in human salmonellosis. Salmonellosis infection typically involves mild and self-limiting gastrointestinal symptoms. However, in approximately 5% of cases, the infection can develop into a serious systemic infection in vulnerable individuals, such as children, elderly and immunocompromised patients, which could lead to a fatal outcome (Acheson & Hohmann, 2001).

NTS is an important cause of bacterial diarrhoea worldwide and the leading cause of foodborne death (Havelaar et al., 2015), with an estimated 80.3 million cases of illness and 155,000 annual deaths worldwide (Majowicz et al., 2010). In the European Union (EU), NTS is the most common bacterial agent involved in foodborne outbreaks –responsible for almost one in three foodborne outbreaks in 2018 (EFSA and ECDC, 2019)–, and the second most common in cases reported, with 87,923 confirmed cases and 926 outbreaks notified in in 2019. The incidence of human salmonellosis has been stable over the last 5 years after a long period of a decline (EFSA and ECDC, 2021a). The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) estimated that the overall economic burden of human salmonellosis could be as high as €3 billion annually (EFSA, 2014). In the UK, NTS infections have an estimated annual cost of £2.12 billion with more than 10,000 laboratory-confirmed cases in 2018. However, 60% of the total foodborne disease cases are of unknown aetiology and have an estimated cost of £6.0bn (Daniel et al., 2020).

2.1.1 Taxonomy of *Salmonella*

There are various taxonomic classification systems for *Salmonella* spp. which have converged on a nomenclature system as the result of their combination. It categorises *Salmonellae* into 2 species (according to (Reeves et al., 1989) and 7 subspecies based on its similar DNA molecular characteristics (set by Le Minor and Popoff in 1987, who named them with Roman numerals I, II, IIIa, IIIb, IV, V and VI), and over 2,500 serovars based on its surface antigens, as defined by the Kauffmann–White scheme. This is the system used by the WHO and maintained by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Reference and Research on *Salmonella* at the Pasteur Institute, when updating the genus with every serovar discovering (EFSA, 2020; Grimont & Weill, 2007).

Following this nomenclature, the genus *Salmonella* (which belongs to the Enterobacteriaceae family), is divided into two species: *S. bongori* and *S. enterica*. *S. enterica* includes six subspecies (Figure 2-1), from which *S. enterica* subspecies *enterica* (or subspecies I, as defined by Le Minor) accounts for the majority of *Salmonella* infections in humans and warm-blooded animals, with most of infections caused by a reduced number of serovars (Anjum et al., 2005; Lan et al., 2009). Therefore, only a small fraction of serovars within subspecies I are responsible for causing disease. The other six subspecies of *S. enterica* and *S. bongori* are usually isolated from cold-blooded animals and the environment, and rare cases in humans are often associated with eating or keeping reptiles as pets (Swearingen et al., 2012).

Figure 2-1. Classification of *Salmonella* spp. into two species, with six subspecies within the enterica species, and over 1,500 known serovars within the subspecies enterica. Some of the more common serovars are *S. Abortusovis*, *S. Enteritidis*, etc. as depicted in the image. Image taken from (Swearingen et al., 2012).

Each *Salmonella* serovar comprises numerous variants that require further classification techniques, like phage-typing. Bacteriophages or phages are virus that infects a narrow range of bacteria. Phage-typing allows differentiation between *Salmonella* variants as each serovar has different susceptibility to a particular phage. For example, in *Salmonella enterica* serovar Enteritidis there are more than 50 different phage types (Humphrey, 2004). This narrower classification can be especially useful in outbreak investigations. The advances to DNA sequencing have extended the use of whole genome sequencing (WGS), replacing other phenotypic and molecular typing tool (Robinson et al., 2013). WGS allows for rapid serovar identification and classification allowing to relate causal agents associated to a same source of infection (Chattaway et al., 2019). This modern approach has been progressively implemented since April 2015 in England and Wales, improving *Salmonella* outbreak surveillance systems (Ashton et al., 2016; McCartney, 2014).

The nomenclature of the genus *Salmonella* is complex and constantly under debate. One of the most extended naming methods, and the one that I will follow in this thesis, responds to the need for uniformity in scientific communications as well as shortening reports. Because most of the diseases of human interest belong to the subspecies *enterica*, *Salmonella spp.* is generally named after the serovar within this subspecies. Hence, *Salmonella enterica* subspecies *enterica* serovar Typhimurium, would be shortened to *S. Typhimurium* (Brenner et al., 2000).

2.1.2 Description of salmonellosis disease

Salmonellosis is generally referred to the disease produced by *Salmonella enterica* subsp. *enterica*. Molecular biology assays have shown that *S. enterica* strains share a high percentage (between 70-100%) of their genetic material (Crosa et al., 1973), suggesting that the bacteria have developed some extent of specialization such as host or niche adaptation, responsible for its variable pathogenesis in different host species.

Some serovars have the ability to invade a wide range of hosts, such as *S. Typhimurium* and *S. Enteritidis* in poultry, swine, cattle and pets, to name a few. They usually cause a mild, self-limiting gastroenteric symptoms in humans and an asymptomatic carrier status in a broad range of animal species, like chicken. These host-unspecific serovars have a larger

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geographical distribution, as a wider range of animals are susceptible to infection and is the most common cause of human infections (Martelli & Davies, 2012). Other serovars are host-specific, such as *S. Gallinarum* or *S. Typhi*, which produce typhoid-like and typhoid fever symptoms in poultry and humans respectively. When a host-specific species causes disease in humans, it is highly invasive and life-threatening. However, as it has no significant animal reservoirs, it has no substantial association with foodborne poisoning if good hygiene measures are maintained and is therefore not within the scope of this thesis.

Therefore, *Salmonella spp.* can be classified into typhoid and non-typhoid regarding its ability to cause specific symptomatology. Non-typhoidal salmonellosis refers to the disease caused by the generalist serovars, which comprise all serovars of *Salmonella enterica* I except for Typhi and Paratyphi (Healy & Bruce, 2020). These serovars responsible for most human infections are commonly called “*Salmonella*” without italics. Like typhoid fever, illness has a non-specific gastric manifestation —such as acute diarrhoea, abdominal pain, fever, and vomiting— but a less severe clinical form in comparison. The incubation period is typically of 6 to 72 hours, although atypical illness has been documented even 16 days after exposure. The illness usually lasts 4 to 7 days, and most people recover without treatment nor medical attention (Healy & Bruce, 2020). Although uncommon, NTS can get complicated when sensitive human hosts harbour the bacteria, such as elderly, pregnant, infants, young children and immunocompromised individuals. Complications may result in extra intestinal infection, such as meningitis, arthritis, endocarditis, osteomyelitis, general septicaemia, and even death.

2.1.3 NTS and main serovars found in Europe and UK

The history of *Salmonella* epidemiology shows that the prevalence of different serovars changes over time, often following changes in husbandry and other practices, such as vaccination and reinforcement of biosecurity measures in farms in the case of *S. Enteritidis* (Barrow et al., 2012), but also with a decline of some strains without any apparent reason such as *S. Agona* in the 1960's (McCoy, 1975). New epidemics can occur any time following the emergence of new or alteration of an existing strain (T. Humphrey, 2004).

S. Enteritidis has been the most commonly reported serovar in the EU for many years (Greig & Ravel, 2009) and the main serovar implicated in human cases of infection (95.9% of reported

cases) (DE KNEGT et al., 2015) followed by *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic *Typhimurium*¹, *S. Infantis* and *S. Newport* (EFSA and ECDC, 2019). Similarly in the UK, *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* are the two most common serovars involved in human disease with the following most common ones varying from year to year (Defra, 2009). Cases of *S. Enteritidis* infection in England and Wales exhibited a sharp rise of cases in the mid 1980's coinciding with the implementation of phage typing techniques in 1981, additionally to centralized reporting systems. This led to the highest ever reported incidence of *S. Enteritidis* in humans from 1988 to 1998 (Figure 2-2). More than half of these cases were caused by *S. Enteritidis*, and more specifically, by phage type 4 (Lane et al., 2014), which is the most common phage type observed in Western Europe (EFSA, 2006; Nygård et al., 2004). Apart from the challenge of detecting *S. Enteritidis* infections in hens due to the absence of clinical signs, it has been hypothesized that this increase may be attributed to the combination of one or more causes: i) the introduction of infected laying hens from other countries into susceptible flocks. After the eradication of the poultry-adapted serovars *Pullorum* and *Gallinarum*, a new niche became available for *S. Enteritidis* (Ward et al., 2000); ii) the reduction of the number of hens resistant to the antigenically similar *S. Pullorum* serovar, which could also protect against *S. Enteritidis* (Ward et al., 2000); and/or iii) the emergence of a new, more virulent strains (Cogan & Humphrey, 2003; Rabsch et al., 2001). Since 1998, the incidence of *S. Enteritidis* has shown a significant and continuous decline, primarily attributed to the introduction of various control strategies. This decline has been less pronounced in the recent years (Lane et al., 2014).

¹ Monophasic *S. Typhimurium* is an antigenic variant of *S. Typhimurium* (*i.e.*, a genomic deletion in the phase II flagellum locus). Even though *S. Typhimurium* is a closely related group, they contain variants that exhibit distinct phenotypes associated with virulence and epidemiology (Arnold et al., 2021) mainly characterised by an increase in multi-drug resistance. It is highly linked to pork and has become a widely spread agent, acquiring a global public health emergency status (Defra, 2009; Lane et al., 2014).

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Figure 2-2. Most common *Salmonella enterica* serovars and total *Salmonella* cases reported in England and Wales for 1945-2011. Three reporting periods are evident: emergence stage, 1982-1987; epidemic stage, 1988-1998; decline stage, 1999-2011. Source (Lane et al., 2014).

The remarkable decline of *S. Enteritidis* in the UK is a good example of a successful national control strategy, which included improved surveillance, hygiene and biosecurity measures in chicken reared for meat (broiler) and laying chicken farms. Control strategies included compulsory flock testing, improved biosecurity standards, bacteriological testing, and most notably, vaccination. Initially, vaccination was performed against *S. Enteritidis* and later against *S. Typhimurium*, in both broiler (1994) and laying flocks (1998) (Cogan & Humphrey, 2003; Defra, 2007, 2009). Testing efforts have remained since then. The “Lion Mark”, as a food safety scheme, was reintroduced in 1998 to guarantee the quality of egg production from vaccinated hens. This scheme encouraged the production and consumption of safe retail eggs, ensuring compliance with the highest safety standards². Between 2007 and 2010, four National Control Programmes (NCP) for the control of *Salmonella* with specific seroprevalence reduction targets have been implemented in the UK (Griffin & O’Brien, 2013). From 2011 to 2019, the levels of NTS laboratory reports have remained relatively constant (UKHSA, 2021).

Salmonellosis cases detected within the EU predominate over cases with a known link outside the EU. According to the ECDC, around 7% of salmonellosis reported in the EU had a confirmed infection link outside the EU between 2017 and 2019, with 25% of cases having an undefined origin (EFSA and ECDC, 2022). This is in contrast with the UK alone, where 56% of cases were acquired within the country with the remaining cases linked to travel mainly in Spain (EFSA

² British Lion eggs scheme: <https://www.egginfo.co.uk/british-lion-eggs>

and ECDC, 2017). The ease of movement of people and goods in Europe undoubtedly contributes to the spread of diseases and makes it challenging to identify the exact source causing outbreaks, but thanks to phage typing efforts, source attribution and increased use of whole genome sequencing, multi-country outbreak investigations are possible.

2.1.4 Sources of human NTS infection

Salmonella is transmitted via the faecal-oral route, mainly through the consumption of food contaminated with bacteria from infected animals (Li et al., 2019). In quantitative terms, pigs and poultry are the primary food animals that serve as source of *Salmonella* spp. (Fedorka-Cray et al., 2000) (Aserkoff et al., 1970; Vandeplass et al., 2010). The environment acts as a medium for pathogens present in the faeces of infected animals to contaminate directly or indirectly the soil, water or animal product, allowing the bacteria to reach the food chain at any point, from production to distribution and serving establishments (Wales et al., 2007).

The main identified food products involved in infection are eggs, meat (chicken, turkey, and pork) and its derivatives (e.g., bakery products cold cuts) (EFSA and ECDC, 2022). Additionally, other food products, such as milk, fruits, and vegetables eaten raw have increasingly been identified as source of disease when contaminated by soil or water (H. Liu et al., 2018). In UK the prevalence of *Salmonella* in beef cattle from abattoir data was estimated in 0.2% (95% CI 0 to 0.5 %) in 1999-2000 (Davies et al., 2004) and 0.43% (95% CI 0.34 to 0.54) in dairy cattle cases per farm-year at risk between October 1999 and February 2001 (Davison et al., 2005). Sprouts, herbs and spices, however, presented higher levels of reported contamination (Park et al., 2018; Wales et al., 2007), presumably due to contamination (e.g., by irrigation or use of faecal wastes as fertilisers). Less common human-to-human and pet-to-human transmission is possible (WHO, 2018). The infective dose is 10^5 to 10^8 CFU/g³, but it can be as low as 1 CFU/g, depending on the age and health status of the host as well as the *Salmonella* serovar (T. Humphrey, 2004).

³ A CFU is defined as a single, viable propagule that produces a single colony (a population of the cells visible to the naked eye) on an appropriate semisolid growth medium (Ujváry, 2010).

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Salmonella serovars can be associated with a predominant animal vehicle —and therefore also with its related food product— as particular agent of disease. For example, in the EU monophasic *S. Typhimurium* is often linked to broiler and pig sources; *S. Newport* to turkey meat; and *S. Enteritidis* primarily to broiler and layers, followed by turkey sources to a lesser extent (EFSA and ECDC, 2019). However, the prevalence of serovars in different sources varies by country and food production practices. At the same time, many salmonellosis outbreaks are not attributable to a single food source given the numerous ingredients present in mixed foods (Pires et al., 2010), and due to the likely more numerous and less investigated sporadic cases not linked to an outbreak (Greig & Ravel, 2009).

Complex foods⁴ (42.26%), poultry⁵ (22.59%) —from which the majority comes from chicken meat (*Gallus gallus*) (EFSA and ECDC, 2017)—, eggs (14.44%) and red meat⁶ (10.67%) were the food vehicles involved in most (89.96%) of all the *Salmonella* outbreaks in Europe (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards, 2008b), very similar to the food at risk identified in England and Wales (Adak et al., 2005). These facts, together with other studies done in Europe, attributed eggs, poultry meat (broiler and turkey) and pork (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards, 2008a; Pires et al., 2010, 2014) as the main sources attributed to human salmonellosis, made us focus our analysis on these foods.

2.1.4.1 Eggs

Table eggs are considered the main source of *S. Enteritidis* (EFSA and ECDC, 2018). In 2018, 45.6% of the reported salmonellosis outbreaks in the EU were associated with the consumption of eggs or egg-containing products (EFSA and ECDC, 2021a). Additionally, raw egg-based sauces, such as mayonnaise and aioli, are frequently linked to *Salmonella* outbreaks. In a case-control study performed in England and Wales in 1988, eggs were largely attributable as main source of infection (Lane et al., 2014). In the UK, most of the egg-

⁴ Includes dishes consisting of ingredients of various food types in which the precise source of infection was not verified.

⁵ Includes chicken, turkey and mixed or unspecified products.

⁶ Includes beef, pork, bacon/ham, lamb and mixed or unspecified products.

mediated human salmonellosis have a catering origin, where the wholesale eggs are often imported (Gormley et al., 2012).

Eggs can get infected vertically during their formation (*i.e.*, transovarian infection) or horizontally, through faecal contamination when passing through the cloaca during oviposition, or when in contact with a contaminated environment (Gantois et al., 2009). *S. Enteritidis* is mostly implicated in the vertical transmission given its ability to invade the reproductive tissues of the chicken, while *S. Typhimurium* (together with other serovars) are usually responsible for eggshell penetration and contamination of the laid egg (Martelli & Davies, 2012). The probability of internal contamination in eggs based on annual incidence study performed in the USA is 10^{-5} . Most eggs are not internally contaminated, but cross-contamination of other foods may occur if they come into contact with an externally contaminated eggshell. Moreover, the survival of *Salmonella* on the shell may be increased by storing the eggs in higher humidity and low temperature storage conditions (*i.e.*, fridge). This external contamination with *S. Enteritidis* is expected to be between 0-19%. (Mokhtari et al., 2006).

Albumen is the principal site of contamination of *S. Enteritidis*, which can remain dormant in eggs stored at ambient temperature for 2-3 weeks (Grijnspeerdt et al., 2005). During that time, physical and chemical changes take place in the egg, such as alterations in the structure of the yolk membrane (which increases its permeability allowing the filtration of nutrients into the albumen) and migration of the yolk towards contaminated air sacs. After reaching the vitelline membrane and the yolk, *S. Enteritidis* multiplies exponentially given the high amount of nutrients available (Gantois et al., 2009; Martelli & Davies, 2012). The permeability of the yolk increases with time (*i.e.*, days after laying) and temperatures above 10°C. The rate of growth of *Salmonella* in the egg also depends on time and temperature (FAO/WHO, 2002; T. J. Humphrey et al., 1991).

The contamination of eggs depends on many factors, such as vaccination status of laying flock, the country of origin of egg, contamination rates, etc. Ultimately, the risk of human infection following consumption of contaminated eggs will depend on the number of bacteria present, which, in turn, depends on the initial contaminant concentration, time and storage conditions.

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Recommendations for storage temperature are set $<10^{\circ}\text{C}$, with minimal temperature fluctuation (Martelli & Davies, 2012). The role of eggs under the influence of temperature as a source of salmonellosis cases will be discussed in Chapter 8.

2.1.4.2 Chicken meat

Broiler meat is the second most important known source of human salmonellosis in Europe after eggs (EFSA and ECDC, 2018). In the UK, chicken is the most consumed type of meat with 28.5kg/person/year, according to Eurostat 2002 (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards, 2008a). Despite the low prevalence of salmonellosis in broiler carcasses in the UK compared to the rest of the EU (3.6% of estimated prevalence (1.7-7.2 95% CI) (EFSA, 2010)), the high consumption rate coupled with potential cross-contamination represent a high risk of infection. Approximately 2% of chicken consumed in a domestic setting present viable cells of *Salmonella* (Stocker et al., 2001).

The risk of salmonellosis is fundamentally linked to under-cooking practices and cross-contamination of other foods. Despite broiler meat being an important source of *Salmonella* contamination, the risk of infection can be mitigated through usual cooking practices that ensure the destruction of the bacteria present on the meat (EFSA, 2007). Compared with eggs, we could conclude that raw chicken has higher levels of contamination, yet eggs are associated with larger outbreaks (Barrow et al., 2012). This is probably due to eggs being usually mixed when manipulated in bulk (*i.e.*, liquid egg for catering) and causing the contamination of an entire batch, whilst meat is more often presented in smaller individual portions.

Salmonella can multiply in broiler chicken as a function of temperature, moisture content and muscle pH. The optimum pH range for salmonella multiplication is 7-7.5 (FAO/WHO, 2002). Oscar conducted an experimental study to model the growth of *Salmonella* in minced chicken breast meat as a function of time and temperature (10°C to 40°C). The study also considered the presence of competitive microflora and utilized a low initial concentration of *S. Typhimurium* ($10^{0.6}$ CFU/g) to provide a more realistic representation of real-world conditions (Oscar, 2006). In the experiment, an initial small inoculum was used for a closer reproduction of the usual initial contamination in chicken carcasses, which is >30 CFU/g (Oscar, 2005).

Temperature values allowing bacterial growth were measured. However, the model presents the limitations of competitive microflora present in the chicken flesh as well as a minimum temperature (5.65°C) under which bacterial growth was not measured nor expected. These and other previous studies were used to model *Salmonella* growth in raw poultry stored under aerobic conditions at variable temperatures (Dominguez & Schaffner, 2008). Using mixed-media and substrate growth data that most closely resembled real conditions, the authors found conflicting growth rates from previous models where pure cultures were used (Juneja et al., 2007; Oscar, 2007). However, what is most notable is that they found no difference in growth rate when high (10^3 CFU/cm²) and low (≤ 10 CFU/cm²) initial inoculums were used. The role of chicken meat under the influence of temperature as a source of salmonellosis cases will be discussed as well in Chapter 8.

2.1.4.3 Pork

Pork meat is the second most consumed type of meat in the UK with 25.3 kg/person/year, according to Eurostat database 2002 (EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards, 2008a). A study evaluating the food source attribution of intestinal infections from outbreaks in England and Wales estimated pork as one of the lowest risks of disease producing meat (Adak et al., 2005). However, in a national survey study which objective was to estimate the prevalence of faecal carriage of *Salmonella* in different healthy food animal species (cattle, sheep and pigs) found that “The caecal *Salmonella* carriage rate in pigs was high at 23.0% (higher than in the rest of the species), although carcasses were only moderately contaminated (5.3%) (Davies et al., 2004). Nonetheless, fermented, ready-to-eat sausages, minced meat and pork meat preparations present the higher risk of contamination due to high manipulation and high ratio volume-surface (*i.e.*, greater surface available for bacterial growth).

2.1.4.4 Tomatoes

Fruits and vegetables are a common source of salmonellosis infection given the degree of handling they undergo prior to raw consumption, which increases the chances of contamination. Tomato has been identified as source of several outbreaks in the United States (Bennett et al., 2015). A model describing *Salmonella* growth rate in cut tomatoes as a function of temperature (Pan & Schaffner, 2010) could potentially be used as a proxy for similar fruits

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and vegetables consumed raw. Moreover, they concluded that the *Salmonella* strains used in their experiments (Typhimurium, Newport, Javiana, and Braenderup) were not as sensitive to the reduced pH of tomatoes as expected.

2.1.5 Infection rates in food animals

Laying hens have been proven to be the main reservoir of the strains of *Salmonella* involved in human disease through contaminated eggs (Cardoso et al., 2021). This fact supports the approach of using animal surveillance data as a strategy to prevent and control disease in humans. A prevalence study performed in the UK in 2004-2005 estimated the prevalence of *Salmonella* on layer farms at 11.9% (CI 95% 9.9-14.7%), from which 7.9% (CI 95% 6.2-10.1%) were positive for *S. Enteritidis* and/or *S. Typhimurium* (Defra, 2007). However, the most frequently isolated *Salmonella* serovars found in farm animals do not necessarily match the most common agents of infection in humans (APHA, 2021; EFSA, 2007). A source attribution study performed in England and Wales in 2021 from laboratory-confirmed human cases and livestock samples identified pigs as the main contributor to human infection for *S. Typhimurium*/monophasic *S. Typhimurium*, with approximately 60% of human cases attributed to them, followed by cattle, turkey and broilers (Arnold et al., 2021).

The greatest benefits of reducing *Salmonella* infection levels have been obtained from the implementation of controls at farm-to-retail processing rather than in domestic kitchens, where the estimated impacts, although still important, are much smaller in scale (Adak et al., 2005). Considering the evidence linking human salmonellosis incidence rates with *S. Enteritidis* prevalence in laying hens in the EU (Havelaar et al., 2013), the benefits of animal disease monitoring become evident. This is particularly relevant given the shared infection pathway that the environment represents for both (Mølbak et al., 2014).

Two important mechanisms of persistence in laying farms could be linked to the ability of *Salmonella* to colonise other animals considered to be pests in farms, such as rodents, birds and insects, and synergism with parasites present in laying farms, such as the red mite or *Ascaris galli* or *Heterakis gallinarum*. It has been confirmed that *Dermanyssus gallinae* (red mite) can act as a vector for *Salmonella* (Valiente Moro et al., 2009). And this is in line with the higher incidence summer peaks, since the mite reproduces faster in hot and humid

conditions. Their life cycle takes a couple of weeks when the temperature is in the 10-20°C range, and decreases to less than a week with temperature between 25-30°C and 70% relative humidity (Sparagano & Giangaspero, 2011). This makes the task of getting rid of red mites much more difficult in hot weather and therefore increases the chances of disseminating *Salmonella* both within and between farms. Another example is transmission through *Ascaridia galli*, a parasitic roundworm linked to organic farming that has increased its presence in Europe due to the ban of battery cages (Marchiondo et al., 2019). Attachment to the external cuticle of the worms, to its eggs externally and potentially internally could appoint to *Salmonella* persistence be potentiated by the presence of *Ascaris* or other parasites (Chadfield et al., 2001), making summer a high peak of parasitism, where higher stress levels associated to higher temperatures suppresses immune system of hens and, by extension, increase *Salmonella* infection, especially in organic or free-range farming systems.

2.2 Seasonality, environment, and *Salmonella*

Seasonality, defined as the fluctuation in number of cases corresponding to a relevant calendar period, is characteristic of many diseases of public health interest (Fisman, 2007), including *Salmonella*. *Salmonella* can grow at temperatures ranging from 7.5 to 37°C, with an optimum at 35-37°C. Thus, *Salmonella* is well adapted to the intestinal conditions of its host, where it finds optimal growing conditions (*i.e.*, 35-37°C, pH of 6.5-7.5, a_w 0.99). However, *Salmonella* has a stress-response mechanism that allows them to adapt to hostile external conditions improving their chances of surviving environment changes, such as low available water or high sunlight exposure (Humphrey, 2004), making them a ubiquitous bacterium. *Salmonella* enters in a viable but non-culturable state in these stressful situations.

An experiment conducted to evaluate the acid and heat tolerance of *S. Enteritidis* to a temperature rise from 20 to 45°C showed that acid tolerance was reached within 5 minutes (Humphrey et al., 1993), meaning that temperature would act as a catalyst favouring the survival of *Salmonella* in acidic environments. This was confirmed by another growth kinetic experiment confirming the tolerance of *S. Typhimurium* to organic acids with temperature as a modulator, being the inhibitory effects of the acidulants diminished for temperatures in the range of 10-37°C (Álvarez-Ordóñez et al., 2012). It has also been described that acid adaptation, in addition to enhancing acid tolerance itself, also reduced the susceptibility of *S.*

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Typhimurium to refrigeration temperatures, allowing bacterial growth at lower temperatures than usual (Shen et al., 2007).

Despite animals being the main reservoir of *Salmonella*, it can also survive in the environment for a long time (Spector & Kenyon, 2012). In fact, it has been observed to survive in aquatic environments by residing with free-living protozoa, vertebrate and invertebrate animals (H. Liu et al., 2018; Lotfy et al., 2011). There is also evidence of seasonal patterns of *Salmonella* abundance in rivers, streams, and ponds that correspond to warmer water ambient temperature and rain events (Baoguang et al., 2014; Haley et al., 2009; Naumova et al., 2007). These events coincide with the end of the summer, which is typically associated with a higher incidence of human salmonellosis. In an effort to reduce the risk of infection from animal to the food chain, the survival of *Salmonella* on farmland has also been studied, with the bacteria found to survive up to three months in slurries and dirty water (Nicholson et al., 2005) and one month in sandy or clay soils (Russell et al., 2022).

2.2.1 *Weather and Salmonella*

The environment is the physical link between a susceptible individual and the agent of disease, which determines the success of a pathogen in inducing disease. Environmental factors can influence the survival and persistence of the pathogen or contaminated object, as well as modulate host-factors that increase exposure, such as animal infection or human practices associated to summer (*i.e.*, frequent outdoor activities and less attention to food handling practices). The association between weather and *Salmonella* is a frequent topic of research, yet it is unclear how weather affects *Salmonella*. Possible causes or mechanisms include animal host shedding, enhanced persistence of *Salmonella* in warm temperatures and increased storm events (Haley et al., 2009).

Several studies have investigated the effect of the environmental conditions on *Salmonella* incidence, with special emphasis on temperatures (Cherrie et al., 2018; Fisman, 2007; Liu et al., 2018; Spector & Kenyon, 2012). In England and Wales, a 12.5% increase in salmonellosis (95% CI; 11.6-13.4) was seen for every degree rise over a 6°C threshold (Kovats et al., 2004). Moreover, extreme temperatures and precipitation events have been seen to influence the number of salmonellosis cases in coastal areas (Jiang et al., 2015), most likely linked to running

water from rainfall acting as a mean of transportation of the bacteria (Baoguang et al., 2014; Haley et al., 2009; Huang et al., 2014). At the same time, *S. Enteritidis* has been found to be more sensitive to temperature as compared to *S. Typhimurium* (Kovats et al., 2004), which shows the complexity and variability of the response to weather within this species. In that same study, infection with *S. Typhimurium* was observed to be more common in rural areas and probably linked to environmental contamination (non-food contact). *S. Enteritidis* was more directly related to transmission via food, supporting the hypothesis that temperature influence is closely linked to activities related to food preparation. The study established that the influence of temperature on the transmission of infection was around 35% of all cases of salmonellosis in England and Wales (Kovats et al., 2004).

There is evidence of other less commonly explored weather factors. A moderate correlation was found with sunshine for *S. Enteritidis* (mean $r = 0.54$) and with vapour pressure for *S. Typhimurium* ($r = 0.46$) (Cherrie et al., 2018). Vapour pressure relates to the weight of water vapour contained in the air per unit of surface, and it is a way of measuring the amount of water contained in the air. The maximum amount of vapour in the air is related to the ambient temperature. The higher the temperature, the more vapour the air can hold (Stocker et al., 2001). On the other hand, sunshine could be correlated with sun UV radiation, although it has been proven that UV-B radiation inactivates *S. Typhimurium* by damaging its DNA (Busse et al., 2019). In this case, sunshine would harm rather than benefit bacterial survival. An indirect increase in temperature linked to sunshine could be the explanation (*e.g.*, heating a food container). Other studies in Asia observed significant positive associations of the combined effect of temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, insolation, and increased cloud cover with cases (Park et al., 2018) or hospitalizations due to *Salmonella* (Wang et al., 2018). A multifactorial and interrelated effect of weather variables seems evident. In general, most of the studies examining the impact of weather factors tend to be performed at low spatiotemporal resolution.

2.2.2 *Climate, Salmonella and climate change*

Climate is commonly defined as the effect of weather over a long period of time (Liu et al., 2013). Climate change is assessed using a variety of possible scenarios that consider factors such as population demographics, policy mitigation responses and greenhouse emission

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levels. Scenarios help to understand the complex interactions of climate system, ecosystems and human activities (Moss et al., 2010). There are numerous models that estimate the projected changes in climate variables for each scenario in different countries. The Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) are a pre-established set of future societal scenarios used for standardising studies and communicating results on climate change research. The RCPs cover a comprehensive range of climate change forcing agents available in the literature (van Vuuren et al., 2011), and are labelled after a range of radiative forcing values⁷ to possibly be reached in the year 2100.

The sixth Assessment Report (AR6) from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2021) provides a solid scientific ground on the latest available knowledge on climate change and its impact. As years go by, we get more solid foundations on the current effects of climate change and the possible future scenarios, which involves alterations in temperature and precipitation across the world. According to the AR6, it is likely that a global warming of 1.5-2°C above pre-industrial levels will be reached and even surpassed by the years 2029-2040 for the highest CO₂ emission scenario (RCP 8.5), and 0.5-1% increase in precipitation. More frequent extreme weather events are also expected to occur, together with a rise of sea level.

Given the sensitivity of many infectious agents to weather, climate change is expected to have an impact over people's health. In fact, over half of known human pathogenic diseases can be aggravated by climate change (Mora et al., 2022). Some of the theories explaining this effect include higher proliferation and reproduction rates of the causal agent at higher temperatures, extended transmission season, changes in ecological balances, and climate-related migration of vectors, reservoir hosts, or human populations (Semenza & Menne, 2009). At the same time, some societies will become more vulnerable due to migrations or decreased water sanitation related to higher temperatures and heavy rainfall events (Figure 2-3).

⁷ "The change in the balance between incoming and out- going radiation to the atmosphere caused by changes in atmospheric constituents, such as carbon dioxide." (Moss et al., 2010)

Conceptual diagram illustrating the exposure pathways by which climate change affects human health. Here, the center boxes list some selected examples of the kinds of changes in climate drivers, exposure, and health outcomes explored in this report. Exposure pathways exist within the context of other factors that positively or negatively influence health outcomes (gray side boxes). Some of the key factors that influence vulnerability for individuals are shown in the right box, and include social determinants of health and behavioral choices. Some key factors that influence vulnerability at larger scales, such as natural and built environments, governance and management, and institutions, are shown in the left box. All of these influencing factors can affect an individual's or a community's vulnerability through changes in exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity and may also be affected by climate change.

Figure 2-3. Conceptual diagram illustrating the exposure pathways by which climate change affects human health. Source: (Crimmins et al., 2016): <https://health2016.globalchange.gov/>

The effect of climate change is more obvious for some infectious diseases, such as water-borne diseases associated to floodings and poor water sanitation (Alcayna et al., 2022). However, *Salmonella* is categorized among some of the priority risks in the AR6 with a strong association with air temperature (Akil et al., 2014), especially with heat waves (Milazzo et al., 2016a).

Salmonella's resilience to persist in the environment and its high stress tolerance to temperature change make it a good competitor amongst the foodborne agents. Therefore,

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salmonellosis prevalence is expected to rise due to the direct effect of temperature in microbial multiplication, or as consequence of a change of patterns of food preparation and consumption in warmer temperatures. For example, an increase in the consumption of foods that are easily contaminated such as raw salads or more time spent in activities involving recreational water or camping that could increase exposure to *Salmonella* found in the environment and in incorrectly preserved food (Britton et al., 2010). By 2071-2100, the annual increase of salmonellosis cases in Europe linked only to temperature, based on linear temperature-disease functions, is estimated to be 50% higher than cases based on population alone, with an economic cost for salmonellosis derived from climate change estimated in several hundred million Euro annually (Rupasinghe et al., 2022; Watkiss & Hunt, 2012). The evaluation of the effect of climate based on the simultaneous effect of multiple weather factors is not frequently performed.

2.2.3 Salmonella projections in the climate change scenario for the UK

The expected increase in temperatures in the UK is of 1 to 5°C, and slightly wetter winters and drier summers by 2100. The hottest and driest areas are in the southeast of the country. The uncertainty around temperature outcomes is related to the model and emission scenario considered, with different confidence levels for each of them. This highlights the complex and intricate nature of climate projections. The timing for reaching a mean warming level of 2°C could be as soon as 2029, while 4°C could be reached from the mid 2040's in the model GC3.05-PPE and or the late 2050s based on the model CMIP5 (Bernie et al., 2018).

Because weather and climate are important determinants of disease, it is important to try to estimate future changes in disease patterns related to climate or environmental changes (Kuhn et al., 2020). This can potentially be done by using current weather data to extrapolate the effect of climate on disease in the future. Given the downtrend in salmonellosis cases in the UK, the expected impact of climate change is considered small (Lake 2017), but the uncertainty surrounding it and the societal and economic cost, makes it highly valuable to assess the effects of climate change and provide the best possible preparation in a changing environment. Ideally, the analysis ought to include other potentially relevant and inter-dependent weather factors. This is presented in Chapter 7.

2.3 Modelling infectious diseases

Infectious diseases are a constant threat and a challenge to public health officers. The increasing frequency of new and re-emerging outbreaks are associated with socio-economic, environmental and ecological factors, such as increased international trade, travel and human interaction with wildlife and their habitats (Jones et al. 2008). This highlights the importance of forecasting disease events, transmission, and evolution in a population so that an adequate control intervention can be set promptly.

With computational power, data availability and encouragement of data sharing, modelling is widely utilised by public health authorities, guiding and contributing to policy decision-making (Leonelli & Tempini, 2021). Mathematical models represent reality with equations that can be solved to produce values for a desired output, based on available knowledge. In epidemiological models, the equations aim to simulate how biological events evolve over time. This includes the spread of the infection, such as through airborne or direct contact transmission, the number exposed, and their associated behaviour. They are then used to produce predictions that represent the most likely outcomes of the situation, helping authorities plan the most appropriate response (Overton et al., 2020; Panovska-Griffiths et al., 2021).

Infectious disease modelling often relies on disease surveillance data, as done in this thesis. The way the surveillance is performed can differ greatly depending on the methodology followed and the capacity for data collection, which may vary within a country and between countries, as observed with the surveillance systems in England and Wales and the Netherlands in this thesis. Surveillance data can be aggregated with different spatial or temporal units in response to different objectives of the analysis. A common practice is to aggregate the observed cases in a weekly (Oberheim et al., 2020) or monthly (Schmidt & Tirado, 2001) fashion. Aggregations over one or more years (Subak, 2003), are thought to take a different approach as they investigate the effect of climate trends, rather than the effect of weather over a shorter period of time. The choice of spatial resolution will depend on the purpose of the analysis, data availability or analysis capacity. The spatial component, population mixing, and mobility patterns may be more relevant for diseases with higher transmissibility (such as airborne diseases like influenza), but it is a component that we cannot

ignore. Data aggregated in larger spatial units can be easier to handle, although can mask some heterogeneity in the population (Servadio et al., 2020) and leading to less accurate population-wide incidence (Mills & Riley, 2014). This has special importance in low density areas. On the other hand, high resolution data (*i.e.*, data collected at small spatial units such as community level) can be valuable in establishing an aetiological link with underlying environmental factors at the expense of computational power. A compromise has to be reached on the size of the spatial unit depending on the nature of the analysis.

Some challenges that arise from modelling are overparameterization (overfitting), biased or low-quality data, and data correlation. When modelling a disease, some decisions need to be taken, including making assumptions to simplify analysis, or discarding incomplete data to avoid drawing incorrect conclusions. The assumptions included in models reflect the best available knowledge of a system. The closer the assumptions are to reality, the better the results of the model to the outcome (Lawson & Marion, 2008). For example, assuming homogeneity in the population of study from different geographic areas. One way to simplify reality is to ignore the differences between clusters that make a population, such as food preferences, cultural eating patterns or the education level to comply with food hygiene standards. This model will not consider an explicit social component on parsimony ground-. Nevertheless, if a social component was correlated with weather factors, the model would implicitly incorporate this component.

2.3.1 Common approaches in disease modelling

Some of the common approaches used to investigate the relationship between an explanatory factor (*e.g.*, environmental variable) and disease occurrence include regression, time series and Bayesian analysis (Barnett & Dobson, 2010). While these techniques prove pragmatic for the purpose of forecasting, they rely on data fitting. This involves employing statistical or machine learning approaches to estimate the parameters of a given model that most effectively explain the provided data.

Regression models can provide useful insights into the underlying relationships between various variables and can help to identify important factors that influence disease forecasting. For example, looking at the association between disease and weather conditions using a

general linear and/or general additive model. Time series models, such as ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average) and its variations (SARIMA, ARMA, ARIMAX, etc.) are routinely used in public health institutions to analyse and predict future disease events based on patterns of previous health data (Imai et al., 2015; Lal et al., 2013; Park et al., 2018). These models assume an accumulative effect in the transmission of a diseases in a population from one day to another, allowing them to make effective and short-term incidence predictions. However, some of the limitations of regression and time series models are their limited ability in capturing non-linear relationships between variables, and reduced capacity to capture the effects of external factors or interaction between variables. For example, the assumption that environmental variables have a linear effect of on disease events. This makes regression models sometimes liable for making spurious correlations and less reliable for forecasting certain diseases. Other techniques, like Bayesian network models, require large amount of data and can be computationally intensive to perform. A variation of linear-regression models of increasing interest for its promising results is the general regression neural network (GNN), which has been shown to outperform traditional regression models (Oscar, 2009).

Compartmental models are a practical type of model used to describe the average progression of a disease in a defined population. Examples include susceptible–infectious–recovered (SIR) and susceptible–exposed–infectious–recovered (SEIR) models, often used in diseases like influenza (Shaman & Karspeck, 2012). These type of models divide the population into compartments based on their disease status and establish specific rates of change between individuals in the compartments (Anderson & May, 1979; Keeling & Rohani, 2007). In this study, we assume a negligible human-to-human transmission when focusing on salmonellosis derived from ingesting contaminated food. Transmission models, however, could be considered if the focus of the study lies on contamination and disease spread within a farm when enough data is available on host, pathogen and environment interaction. Compartmental models can be deterministic or stochastic. Stochastic models provide a range of possible outcomes by incorporating the effect of chance (Bailey, 1975). These models can be computationally heavy and are used when fluctuations due to random effects are important.

2.3.2 Modelling weather and disease data

Other challenges when modelling the effect of weather conditions on disease incidence include identifying the effect of weather on the different pathways of pathogen transmission, cases under-reporting, collinearity of weather variables or the time lag influencing the different staged of disease progression (Lo Iacono et al., 2017). However, investigating seasonal patterns of disease is an effort worth making, as it enables generation of hypotheses regarding aetiology.

Most studies focus their efforts in linking disease events with temperature (Bentham & Langford, 2001; Kovats et al., 2004; Lake et al., 2009), humidity (Xu et al., 2014) or rainfall (Wang et al., 2018). The association of these weather parameters with salmonellosis has been studied in geographic areas from different continents with usually low spatial resolution (Davis et al., 2022). Other variables less commonly studied include snowfall, wind speed, duration of sunshine, insolation, cloudiness and vapour pressure (Cherrie et al., 2018; Park et al., 2018). All these studies agree on the association between salmonellosis and temperature. However, the association with the other weather variables varies in the different studies. Furthermore, the association between salmonellosis and temperature in relation to other weather variables is rarely explored. It is precisely this intricate and multidirectional relationship between weather and salmonellosis that this thesis seeks to investigate and elucidate.

Chapter 3

Methodology

This chapter describes the approaches considered to evaluate the impact of weather and climate on salmonellosis incidence, along with a description of the data used in Chapter 3.1. Chapter 3.2 provides an overview of the principles and concepts used in all the applications explored in the thesis. Each chapter provides adaptations of the methodology for its specific application.

First, a mechanistic approach was conceived to establish a link between relevant weather factors, bacterial growth in food, and foodborne salmonellosis (Chapter 3.2.1). However, data constraints in the literature limited the analysis to a single factor (*i.e.*, temperature), which does not capture the complex effect of weather as a whole. As a result, a statistical model was developed (Chapter 3.2.2). The statistical approach constitutes the main methodology of the thesis, which was then applied in England and Wales, the Netherlands and to a climate change scenario in Chapters 5, 6 and 7 respectively. The order of the applications is presented according to their relevance to the content of the thesis, with the mechanistic chapter intentionally placed towards the end, even though it was conducted first. I will take advantage of its placement at the end of the thesis to compare the results of both mechanistic and statistical approaches.

3.1 Data sources and pre-processing

3.1.1 *Salmonellosis case data*

National surveillance data relies on medical practitioners and laboratories to diligently notify cases to health authorities to collect routine laboratory data on infectious diseases (Second Generation Surveillance System) (Severi et al., 2014). Salmonellosis notification is mandatory in England and Wales (UKHSA, 2022), with a case typically confirmed by microbial culture at a diagnostic laboratory.

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Despite the availability of good estimates, such as the Infectious Intestinal Disease (IID2) study in the UK (Tam et al., 2012), the true burden of salmonellosis remains unknown due to a significant degree of reporting bias in case reporting (Havelaar et al., 2013). In response to a food poisoning event, individuals may not seek medical care, preventing their illness to be diagnosed or reported to public health authorities –under-ascertainment–. In other cases, individuals may seek medical care but fail to receive a definite diagnosis or may not be officially registered –underreporting– (Gibbons et al., 2014). The underestimation of cases that leads to a reduced proportion of reported cases can be illustrated with a “surveillance pyramid” (Figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1. Foodborne disease surveillance pyramid. Source: (WHO, 2017).

The proportion of cases not recorded by national laboratory surveillance can be large and varies by microorganism. Different ways of estimating the true burden of disease have been published elsewhere (Havelaar et al., 2013; Tam et al., 2012; Wheeler et al., 1999). These estimations vary greatly depending on the methodology followed, data available and time of performing the calculations. This number may well be different if the study was repeated at the present. Therefore, when estimating the risk of infection based on the weather conditions in this thesis, I am not aiming to determine the exact number of cases in the community, but rather the probability of detecting a case considering the current surveillance and reporting situation. Assuming that weather does not affect spatio-temporal reporting patterns, the probability of detecting a case of salmonellosis would exhibit a correlation with weather akin

to an actual case. This correlation might involve an under-reporting correction factor that remains constant over time and uniform across locations. Furthermore, I assumed that under-ascertainment and under-reporting bias is based on similar behavioural patterns that remain continuous from year to year (*e.g.*, similar rate of medical visits, absence of significant control strategies that would imply a variable case-reporting rate, etc.). This assumption can be too restrictive, to ensure its validity I selected only surveillance data under similar public health intervention (*i.e.*, after year 2000, Figure 3-2) and adjusted the data to remove temporal trend (see Chapter 4). Daily laboratory-confirmed salmonellosis cases collected through national surveillance by UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA) between 1989 and 2020 were provided by collaborators from UKHSA (Figure 3-2).

Figure 3-2. Laboratory-confirmed salmonellosis cases reported to UKHSA from 1989-2020 at a daily resolution. Seasonal pattern observed for every year. The implementation of vaccination strategies in 1998 coincides with a steep decrease in cases reported after 2000. A progressive steady decline of the number of cases can be observed throughout the time series.

Figure 3-3. Cumulative laboratory-confirmed salmonellosis cases per month of specimen date summed for the years 1989-2020. A seasonal pattern is identifiable with a peak in cases during the months of August and September.

For each case, the data included specimen date (*i.e.*, date when the human sample was collected from the patient (UKHSA, 2022)), type of specimen, diagnostic laboratory name and location, sex and age of the patient, linkage with travel, *Salmonella* serovar and phage type. Confidential patient information was removed before the reception of the data to ensure compliance with data confidentiality. The year 2000 was chosen as the first year of the study, set two years after the introduction of the *Salmonella* vaccination program in laying hens,

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which ensured a consistent level of surveillance throughout the time series. See Appendix A for an exploratory analysis of the influence of the years on the model outcomes. The final year was set in 2016 to coincide with the latest year for which high-resolution demographic data were available. Cases with a known travel linkage, without a clear link with a diagnostic laboratory in England and Wales (namely, pseudo-postcodes probable to be linked with an overseas address, *i.e.*, visitors getting infected in the UK, such as “ZZ993CZ”, “Z993CZ” (England not specified), “ZZ993HZ”(Channel Islands), and “ZZ993WZ” (address unknown or inadequately described)⁸) were excluded. Cases produced by a *Salmonella* serovar of non-foodborne concern (*i.e.*, subspecies other than *Salmonella* sp. *enterica* ssp. *enterica*⁹, as well as typhoidal *Salmonella* (ssp. *enterica* serovars Typhi, Paratyphi types, and Java variant) were also excluded (Figure 3-4).

⁸ Source: Office for National Statistics: <https://digital.nhs.uk/services/organisation-data-service/file-downloads/office-for-national-statistics-data>

⁹*Salmonella* subspecies belonging to the enterica species that were removed: *ssp. salamae* (II) (Sofia, Ottershaw, Fremantle, Uphill, Khami, Degania, Ngozi, Lichtenberg, Nordenham, Detroit, Nairobi, Mjimwema, Negev, Haddon, Lethe, Tosamanga, Phoenix, Canastel, Makoma, Rhodesiense, Hagenbeck, Erlangen, Makumira, Hillbrow, Mosselbay, Bilthoven, Dubrovnik, Luanshya, Hueningen, Bechuana, Limbe, Caledon, Bloemfontein, Zuerich, Woerden, Lundby, Wynberg, Suarez, Bleadon, Veddell, Tygerberg, Merseyside, Quimbamba, Nachshonim, Fuhlsbuettel, Wandsbek, Katesgrove, Alsterdorf, Rowbarton, Zeist, Rand, Gwaai, Namib, Salamae); *arizonae* (IIIa), *diarizonae* (IIIb), *houtenae* (IV) (Marina, Argentina, Wassenaar, Parera, Flint, Lohbruegge, Houten, Tuindorp, Ochsenzoll, Kralendyk, Seminole, Bonaire, Volksdorf, Sachsenwald, Harmelen, Tosamanga, Phoenix, Canastel, Makoma, Rhodesiense, Hagenbeck, Erlangen, Makumira, Hillbrow, Mosselbay, Bilthoven, Dubrovnik, Luanshya, Hueningen, Bechuana, Limbe, Caledon, Bloemfontein, Zuerich, Woerden, Lundby, Wynberg, Suarez, Bleadon, Veddell, Tygerberg, Merseyside, Quimbamba, Nachshonim, Fuhlsbuettel, Wandsbek, Katesgrove, Alsterdorf, Rowbarton, Zeist, Rand, Gwaai, Namib, Salamae); and *bongori* (V) (Bongor). Ssp. *indica* (VI) was not present.

Figure 3-4. Breakdown of the number of cases included in the analysis after filtering for serovars, linkage to travel and years of interest. The final salmonellosis surveillance data consisted of 144,703 cases, which were used to feed the statistical model.

3.1.2 Estimation of day of infection

The day when the infection most likely occurred was used for linking surveillance and weather data for a closer match of the weather conditions at the time of exposure. This date was inferred retrospectively based on the specimen date, taking into account the incubation period (time between exposure to a pathogen and the onset of symptoms), the time it took the patient to seek medical care, and the time it took to submit a specimen to a laboratory.

Figure 3-5. Timeline of the reporting delays that were included to estimate a probable date of infection. Incubation period was adjusted for the three most common serovars following a gamma distribution. Time to healthcare and specimen delay were fit to a normal distribution following CDC estimates for the time to healthcare and expert opinion for the specimen processing time (G. Nichols personal communication).

The duration of the incubation period varies depending on factors, such as the *Salmonella* serotype, food source of infection, the concentration of bacteria ingested, immunity status of the host, etc. Thus, the empirical data of incubation periods tend to follow a statistical distribution. In an effort to approximate the incubation period as accurately as possible, this

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value was drawn from a gamma distribution in hourly precision. The correction for the incubation period was estimated by considering the mean and variance of the incubation periods of the three most commonly reported serotypes: Enteritidis (66.5 h), Typhimurium (54.2 h) and Virchow (103.8 h), which together accounted for 75% of the reported cases. These parameters were used to calculate the shape and scale of the gamma distribution. Additionally, the mean (67.67 h) and mode (30.2 h) of the incubation periods of the remaining serotypes studied in Eikmeier et al. (2018), along with unpublished data provided by Eikmeier personally, were taken into account to correct for the incubation period for the rest of the serotypes reported to the UKHSA. These less common serotypes were used to represent around 900 different serotypes, making the remaining 25% of cases reported to the UKHSA. The time to seek medical care (1-5 days) and the time to submit a specimen to a laboratory (0-1 days) were calculated from a log-normal distribution based on available estimations specific for *Salmonella* (CDC, 2015; Kovats et al., 2004; Severi et al., 2014) and expert opinion (G. Nichols personal communication). In short, the probable date of infection was estimated taking into account both the incubation period and the aforementioned reporting delays retrospectively from the date when the specimen was received. The reporting delay values generated range from 1 to 36, the most common being between 5 and 7 days. (Table 3-1).

Min	1 st Qu.	Median	Mean	3 rd Qu.	Max
1.000	5.000	6.000	6.227	7.000	36.000

Table 3-1. Distribution of the final delay values generated after accounting incubation period and reporting delays of Figure 3-5.

3.1.3 Weather data

Weather data provided by the Met Office were statistically downscaled at the diagnostic laboratory locations via the Met Office Medical and Environmental Data Mash-up Infrastructure (MEDMI) platform (Fleming et al., 2014; Leonelli & Tempini, 2021) through inverse distance weighted (IDW) interpolation. The differences in temperature and rainfall between laboratory and domestic patient addresses are known to be minimal (Djennad et al., 2018), and thus were considered to be negligible for other weather factors. Furthermore, using laboratory addresses as proxy for domestic patient addresses prevent the use of confidential data. From the meteorological data received, nine raw and five calculated daily factors were selected for their potentially relevant influence on the proliferation of *Salmonella*

in the environment (*e.g.*, soil, cooking surfaces) or in food products after they have left the point of sale and are exposed to the weather outside a controlled environment. I considered the effects of warmth, water condensation, water permeability in the food product and microcidal effect of UV-C radiation as relevant processes involved in bacterial proliferation.

Temperature and water availability (or water activity) are two important parameters for bacterial multiplication in food (Santillana Farakos et al., 2013). Given that *Salmonella's* optimal growth temperature is around 37°C, the maximum temperatures reached in a day would be indicative of the degree of bacterial multiplication. Temperature variation, mean temperature and air pressure were explored due to their potential association to effects of water condensation in packaged or ready to eat foods. At the same time, high atmospheric pressure values (>1013 hPa) in summer are usually linked to higher temperatures, while related with thermal inversion and fog in winter. Relative humidity, dewpoint temperature and precipitation were explored as a direct source of water available to *Salmonella*. Dewpoint temperature is related to the ambient temperature and relative humidity, but also depends on air vapour pressure (Davis et al., 2016), so it may imply condensation and higher water activity in foodstuff. Precipitation can also be linked with water overflow and water sources contamination. As a third component, radiation was assessed for its impact on bacterial survival, be it in the form of total daylength, sun exposure or radiation values. Additionally, this factor would indirectly account for the outdoor eating behaviours linked to favourable weather conditions.

Subsequently, maximum and mean air temperature, dew point temperature (*i.e.*, the temperature at which condensation occurs and is dependent upon the humidity and pressure of the air), surface air pressure, relative humidity, mean precipitation, sunshine duration, wind speed, global radiation and total day length were selected. Refer to Table C-1 in the Supplementary material for a descriptive statistics of all the weather factors studied. Temperature variation was calculated by subtracting maximum minus minimum temperature, and cumulative precipitation as the addition of the mean daily precipitation values over the chosen time lag (*i.e.*, 7 days). Given that people remain a good part of the day indoors in modern societies (Schweizer et al., 2007), I also assessed the effect of indoor temperature and humidity conditions in the incidence of salmonellosis (indoor relative humidity and indoor

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temperature). These were based on the equations developed in (Verheyen & Bourouiba, 2022) from the outdoor values and an assumed thermal comfort of 21°C. Therefore, a baseline of 21°C was adopted for situations where the outdoors temperature fell below this threshold, while the recorded temperature was considered for instances above it. Day length was calculated from the day of the year, and the latitude of the laboratories (Forsythe et al., 1995) and assessed as another weather factor, even if it is technically an astronomical measure. All the weather factors were explored in a total of 57 different combinations. An overview of the records for maximum air temperature, precipitation, global radiation and day length can be seen below (Figure 3-6, Figure 3-8, Figure 3-9). Refer to Appendix C for a description of the complete weather dataset.

Figure 3-6. Overview of the daily maximum air temperature for the years analyzed (2000-2016). All the laboratories' locations are displayed with a dot that conforms the overall temperature curves. The color-code provides a graphical representation of the temperature variation.

Figure 3-7. Distribution of maximum air temperature values recorded per season (2000-2016). The spread of the distribution of their values reflects the thermal amplitude of winter, spring and autumn, as opposed to the smaller variation observed in summer.

Figure 3-8. Daily mean precipitation values at every catchment area across England and Wales. The year 2000 is displayed as a representative. Precipitation is very variable in a year, with no clear trend. Some isolated days of higher precipitation can be observed, such as mid July 2008. In blue, a generalized additive model (gam) smoother that shows a higher amount of precipitation from October to December approximately. The color-code provides a graphical representation of precipitation variation.

Figure 3-9. Mean (red bold), 25 and 75 quantile values (red ribbon) of global radiation for the years of study (2000-2016) in relation with the duration of the days. The yellow line represents daylength averaged for the latitudes of all locations.

The effect that weather may have on the occurrence of a disease is likely not attributable to a single factor, but rather to an ensemble of cumulative conditions (*e.g.*, effect on the bacterial community and/or people behaviour). A previous study in England have set a lag of 2-5 weeks between a weather and disease event (Lake et al., 2009). However, the study was focused on the effect of temperature alone over the *S. Typhimurium* serotype. To account for the time that it takes for weather to result in infections (*i.e.*, the cumulative effect of conditions over multiple days as opposed to an isolated instance), I performed a rolling average of the weather conditions from 7 days prior to the day of infection. Other lags of 2, 7, 14, 21, 30 and 60 days were explored with qualitatively similar results (Appendix F).

3.1.4 Catchment areas

The spatial area chosen to link weather, disease and population data was the catchment areas delimited by UKHSA (Lo Iacono et al., 2024). They consist of the area around the 216 diagnostic laboratories to which they provide coverage (Figure 3-10). Salmonellosis events were linked to the catchment area of the diagnostic laboratory reporting the case instead of the patient’s address, due to data protection as well as to avoid discarding instances with missing or incomplete patient address. This was based on the fact that patient’s specimen would be

generally sent to the reference laboratory nearest to their typical place of residence. See Appendix D for further detail on the post code data rendering.

Figure 3-10. **Left:** spatial distribution of the diagnostic laboratories within England and Wales. A higher concentration of laboratories is located in the most densely population areas. **Right:** Catchment areas inferred from referrals on campylobacteriosis (Lo Iacono et al., 2024) and defined upon patient domestic address. Each colour represents a different catchment area assigned to a diagnostic laboratory.

3.1.5 Population data

The number of residents of each catchment area (N_H) were estimated from information of the usual resident mid-year population estimates by Nomis¹⁰ at the Lower Super Output Area (LSOA)¹¹ resolution. These data were provided by the GIS (Geographic Information System) team at UKHSA at yearly resolution. The resident information was used to calculate the estimated incidence of salmonellosis in a catchment area.

3.2 Analysis methods: Modelling salmonellosis incidence

The methodology used in this thesis builds on the conditional incidence developed by (Lo Iacono et al., 2024), where the probability of cases reported (risk of salmonellosis) is calculated on the basis of weather and number of residents, as sole explanatory factor. The initial mechanistic approach aimed to link the effect of weather on bacterial proliferation in the main

¹⁰ Official census service from the Office for National Statistics (ONS)

¹¹ Lower Layer Super Output Areas, the smallest demographic unit created by the ONS.

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food sources involved in disease. This approach was then complemented by a statistical one due to the lack of available published data on the effect of weather factors other than temperature. The statistical approach explored a wider effect of weather as the result of the combined interaction of different factors. Both approaches followed a similar methodology, with some variations described in the next subchapters. Numerical codes and parameters were built in R software version 4.0.2 (R Core Team, 2022). The R scripts used for this model and all of its applications are available on an open-access repository¹².

Infections by *Salmonella* during a given time are considered random, countable, and discrete events, independent one from another. In other words, it is assumed that the probability of one person being infected does not directly influence the probability of another person getting infected. This assumption is based on the notion that person-to-person transmission is considered negligible and that there are numerous pathways involved in the infection process, such as cross-contamination of domestic cooking surfaces, cracking of eggs on the same eating plate, etc. I have also made the assumption that the frequency at which events occur is influenced by underlying environmental conditions, and as such, it can be estimated accordingly.

Thus, the probability of detecting a *Salmonella* infection at a specific catchment area was modelled as a **Poisson process**, a special case of binomial distribution commonly used when modelling count data. Poisson processes are used to account for the occurrence of random events that happen independently at a certain rate λ_p , the expected number of infections per time-period. This approach allows to estimate the probability to observe k number of salmonellosis infections during a time interval τ (here chosen as one day) according to:

$$p(k) = e^{-\lambda_p \tau} \frac{(\lambda_p \tau)^k}{k!}. \quad \text{Equation 3-1}$$

A feature of Poisson processes is the equality of the mean and variance of the modelled data. Empirical data, however, tend to be overdispersed (*i.e.*, their variance is larger than the mean). To account for this effect, the use of a negative binomial distribution is often advocated instead of Poisson distribution. Nonetheless, overdispersion naturally arises from a Poisson

¹² https://github.com/lauracris-7/Conditional_Incidence_Salmonella

distribution when the rate is itself a stochastic term. In particular, a negative binomial distribution is equivalent to a Poisson distribution when its rate is drawn from a gamma distribution. In our situation, given the freedom of values that λ_p can take for the many different weather combinations and the stochastic nature of the values of the different weather factors, λ_p becomes a random variable. The empirical distributions of the rate λ_p (at least for some of the catchment areas explored here) were well approximated by gamma distributions and thus, the modelled salmonellosis data can be described by a Gamma-Poisson mixture distribution, or in other words, a negative binomial distribution. Furthermore, the estimated number of cases were significantly lower in comparison to the overall population in each catchment area, naturally leading to a zero-inflated distribution of the modelled data.

Most of the work here focuses on the expected daily number of salmonellosis cases in each catchment area, λ_p , rather than explicit stochastic realisations of Equation 3-1. Two different approaches were used based on the Poisson concept. The first approach modelled the rate λ_p based on the known mechanism for bacteria to grow in food (Chapter Mechanistic analysis 3.2.1), followed by the second approach which estimates the rate λ_p based on the statistical, empirical association of weather and reported cases from 17 years historical data (Chapter 3.2.2).

3.2.1 Mechanistic analysis

Given that food is the main source of transmission of *Salmonella* and temperature is an important variable in food microbiology, the effect of maximum air temperature on bacterial growth in the main products associated with foodborne salmonellosis was analyzed. Undercooked egg and chicken meat/meat products were considered as the main sources of infection (EFSA and ECDC, 2018; Lane et al., 2014).

The expected number of infections per day (rate λ_p) at a certain location, caused by one source of infection (*e.g.*, Equation 3-2):

$$\lambda_p = N_H \cdot P_{contact}^{source} \cdot \chi^{source} \cdot P_R, \quad \text{Equation 3-2}$$

where N_H is the average number of people living in a catchment area, $P_{contact}^{source}$ per capita contact rate with a specific source of infection, χ^{source} probability of getting infected and

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contracting the disease following a contact with the source of infection, and P_R the probability of reporting a disease event following symptoms. When considering multiple sources of infection, Equation 3-2 can be expressed as Equation 3-3:

$$\lambda_p = N_H (P_{contact}^{eggs} \cdot \chi^{eggs} + P_{contact}^{chicken} \cdot \chi^{chicken} + \dots) P_R . \quad \text{Equation 3-3}$$

The probability of an individual coming into contact with an infected source ($P_{contact}^{source}$) depends on the probability of ingesting contaminated food, which, in turn, depends on consumer behaviour. For simplicity, consumption behaviour patterns were assumed constant in time and are uniform across England and Wales. $P_{contact}^{source}$ and P_R are in general unknown. However, assuming that these factors are constant over time and uniform across all catchment areas, the spatio-temporal distribution of actual cases then reflects the spatio-temporal distribution of reporting patterns, except for an unknown overall **coefficient of proportionality**. The **probability of getting infected and contracting the disease** following contact with the source χ^{source} was assumed to be proportional to the maximum bacterial load achievable in the food source given the local weather conditions (*e.g.*, air temperature): the more colony-forming units (CFU) of *Salmonella* present in the food, the greater the likelihood of causing infection and subsequent illness.

Accordingly, χ^{source} and, thus, the rate of infection λ_p , was estimated by calculating the maximum bacterial load for a specific source of infection and for the local air temperature at each catchment area on a daily basis. The possibility for the observed seasonality of infections to be replicated was then assessed. The value of λ_p changes in time and location due to the changing temperature and the diverse population distributed across the catchment areas, making it an **inhomogeneous and stochastic** (due to environmental stochasticity in temperature) **Poisson process**. The rate λ_p ought to incorporate additional source of stochasticity to represent the other numerous factors involved in infection, such as varying eating habits and other human behaviours particular to an area. However, for simplicity, these additional stochastic effects were disregarded. The results of the mechanistic approach are shown in Chapter 8.

3.2.1.1 Bacterial load vs temperature

Many biological processes, such as the growth of plants, tumours, and fish population follow similar growth patterns (Tjørve & Tjørve, 2017). The **Gompertz curve** is a sigmoidal-shaped mathematical function commonly used to describe microbial growth in food over time at static temperature conditions (Longhi et al., 2017). This includes the description of *Salmonella* growth rates in various food products and cooking presentations, including shell eggs, cooked chicken, raw chicken skin, ground sterile pork, ground beef, and brain-heart infusion broth (Juneja et al., 2007; Lobacz et al., 2020; Mokhtari et al., 2006; Oscar, 1999a, 1999b, 2000, 2011).

Zwietering et al. (1990) adapted the mathematical expression of the growth curve with parameters of biological relevance, facilitating the interpretation and usability of microbial models performed under different experimental conditions. The effect of temperature on bacterial growth can be described with the Arrhenius equation, which states that the rate of a chemical reaction (or bacterial growth, in this case) is exponentially proportional to the temperature (Arrhenius, 1889). A modified Ratkowsky model was used to analyse the maximum growth rate (*i.e.*, the highest growth rate achievable when all essential nutrients and environmental factors are at their most favourable levels, μ_{max}) from the modified Gompertz model as a function of temperature, allowing to predict and compare bacterial growth patterns under different temperature conditions (Zwietering et al., 1991):

$$\mu_{max} = a(T - T_{min})^2(1 - \exp(b(T - T_{max}))). \quad \text{Equation 3-4}$$

T is temperature in degrees Celsius, T_{min} and T_{max} are the theoretical temperatures beyond and below which growth of *Salmonella* does not occur, and a and b are regression coefficients. This expression accounts for a decline of bacterial numbers beyond T_{max} (Figure 3-11).

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Figure 3-11. Example of an application of the modified Ratkowsky model built upon growth data estimated from the Gompertz curve. The maximum growth rate of a *Salmonella* serotype cocktail is described as a function of temperature in raw chicken (Juneja et al., 2007).

Specific maximum growth rate values (μ_{max}) of *Salmonella* in the foods of interest found in the literature are used to model the effect of temperature on *Salmonella* growth in Chapter 8.

3.2.2 Statistical analysis

The incidence of salmonellosis conditional to weather values is calculated and compared to empirical incidence data. A combination of three weather factors of interest were selected at a time (*e.g.*, mean air temperature, precipitation and day length). The rationale for analysing the effect of three weather factors simultaneously was to reduce the effect of correlations among weather factors. Based on previous analysis (Lo Iacono et al., 2024), the choice of three factors was sufficient to capture well the empirical patterns of campylobacteriosis and allow predictions. For computational convenience, the weather factors were classified into uniform, discrete bins (Table 3-2).

Weather factor	Units	Range values	Bin size	Range of uniform weather bin	No. of bins
Max. air Temperature	°C	(-2.98) - 28.20	1	(-3)-28	32
Mean air Temperature	°C	-4.82 - 23.91	1	(-5)-23	29
Relative humidity	%	54.09 - 98.69	5	57-97	9
Precipitation	mm	0 - 19.15	0.5	0-13	27

Air pressure (mean surface)	hPa	954.4 - 1035.5	5	954-1034	17
Dewpoint temperature	°C	(-6.19) - 17.92	1	(-6)-18	25
Global radiation	kJ/m2	4.74 - 43589.01	1000	514-30514	31
Day length	h	7.16 - 17.38	1	7-17	11

Table 3-2. Overview of the weather values registered from 2000 to in England and Wales and its categorization into uniform bins. Summary of the range of weather values and the size of uniform bins created to stratify the values in the conditional incidence. Sizes of the bins were chosen according to the size of the weather values range. All weather values are IDW mean.

The model is based on the following steps:

- 1) All infection occurrences (regardless of location and time) were identified.
- 2) Then, I calculated the total number of cases found for a specific weather combination where the weather factors were averaged over certain number of preceding days to account for the ensemble of weather conditions around the day of infection. For example, all situations (days and location) where the average maximum air temperature in the preceding 7 days was between 15 and 16°C, the average precipitation was between 0 and 1 mm, and the average global radiation was between 1000 and 1500 kJ/m² (Figure 3-12).
- 3) The ratio P_{Salm} was estimated as the newly number of cases reported for that specific weather combination out of the total number of residents exposed to the same weather conditions (Equation 3-5).

$$P_{Salm} = \frac{\text{Number infected people}}{\text{Number people exposed to the same weather variables}} \quad \text{Equation 3-5}$$

The ratio P_{Salm} is interpreted as the conditional probability of detecting a new case given the specific weather values. Here and throughout, by **conditional incidence** we refer to the daily probability of detecting a salmonellosis case multiplied by one million.

- 4) The number of residents for each day and location (catchment area) was ascertained, and the weather factors were evaluated by averaging them over a selected number of preceding days (time-lag).
- 5) Finally, the expected number of daily infections (*i.e.*, the term λ_p) for each day and each location was determined by multiplying the corresponding conditional probability of finding a case, given the corresponding weather variables, by the number of residents of the said catchment.

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In a Poisson process framework, the rate of infection corresponds to the expected daily number of salmonellosis cases in the said catchment. Due to stochastic variability in the weather factors, the rate is itself a stochastic parameter which would naturally reproduce overdispersion in the data. In this way, I can reproduce the number of detected cases based exclusively on weather values recorded for each day and location. By comparing modelled and historical reported cases, an evaluation of the performance of the model for different weather factors was conducted. This approach allows to identify optimal combinations of weather factors, or at least to narrow down the pool of suitable factors, which are better associated with salmonellosis and potentially involved in the causal pathway. The results of the statistical approach are shown in Chapter 5, with an application in a different geographic setting in Chapter 6 and for a different climate scenario in Chapter 7. A summary of the methodology followed is represented in Figure 3-13.

Figure 3-12. Graphical summary of the conditional incidence methodology. The probability of finding a case of salmonellosis (P_{Salm}) is the result of dividing the total number of cases reported by all the residents exposed to a same weather combination, both with (N_2) and without cases found in the catchment area (N_1). This division considers the entire 17-year dataset and all catchment areas added up together, meaning that it is not dependent of space or time. The catchment areas in England and Wales are represented as yellow squares when exposed to equivalent weather (e.g., same temperature, precipitation and global radiation category). Image adapted from (Lo Iacono et al., 2024).

3.2.2.1 Differences with previous methodology used for campylobacteriosis

- In the initial study on campylobacteriosis, only maximum and minimum air temperature, rainfall, relative humidity, and mean wind speed were explored. In this thesis, ten more additional factors were considered, resulting in a substantially higher number of combinations implemented and tested.
- The probable date of infection was more closely approximated, by breaking down the reporting delay to include time to healthcare and time to submit a specimen. Moreover, the incubation period drawn considered the differences between the most commonly reported serotypes. A gamma distribution was used as this is the function that closest reproduces incubation periods.
- A more in-depth examination of the trend in the data was conducted, leading to the adjustment of the dataset to remove temporal patterns probably linked to public health intervention and/or change in behavior.
- The performance of the model was appropriately tested in a different country. For this, the model had to be generalized and adjusted for a different surveillance system, spatial units and behavioral patterns, such as the mandatory character of salmonellosis report, recidivist patients, the medical seeking patterns, the severity of the disease based on the sample analysed, and the specific reporting delays.
- The expected incidence of salmonellosis was explored in different weather and climatic scenarios. For this, the operability of the model was adjusted to multiple weather possibilities for its application to climate projections, as well as adding interpolation operations to make the model applicable to weather situations not experienced before.
- The resulting incidence estimates from two different approaches under the influence of temperature were compared: the conditional incidence from mean air temperature alone (statistical) with the cases due to chicken and eggs (mechanistic approach).

Furthermore, the work performed for this thesis helped to improve the analysis of campylobacteriosis in (Lo Iacono et al., 2024) by providing scientific and computational feedback as well as novel R scripts.

Figure 3-13. Diagram of the data manipulation for feeding and applying the conditional incidence statistical model

Chapter 4

Results of a descriptive exploration of reported salmonellosis cases

An epidemiological, descriptive exploration of salmonellosis cases reported during the years studied between 2000-2016 allowed to get a better understanding of the epidemiological profile of patients diagnosed with salmonellosis (age and sex), the prevalence of the main salmonella serotypes identified across the years, as well as to identify temporal reporting biases around weekends and bank holidays. Despite the temporal trend and fluctuating number of cases reported year to year, a seasonal pattern was confirmed through a wavelet analysis. This reassured the rationale for investigating the relationship between salmonellosis and weather. In order to extract the “pure” seasonality and mitigate the influence of reporting biases, a detrending technique is presented to enable comparison of interannual epidemiological data. This technique is used in the subsequent analysis chapters 5 and 6 in order to remove the temporal variability derived from changing diagnostic techniques and reporting behaviours.

4.1 Patient age and sex distribution

The number of reported cases per five-year age category was divided by the total number of residents in that same category¹³ to calculate the proportion of cases for each age group (Figure 4-1). The age group covering 0-4 years was the most affected one, followed with >90 years age group. These seem to be the most vulnerable groups and at greater risk of developing serious symptoms. A reporting bias from higher health screening at the end age

¹³ Demographic data from the Office of National Statistics was available for years 1991 to 2019, so these were the years considered for assessing the distribution of cases by age. The highest age group was set at 90 and over years old, following the ONS classification.

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groups cannot be discarded. Salmonellosis cases were similarly distributed between sexes (Figure 4-2). This is in line to previous UKHSA NTS annual report (UKHSA, 2021).

Figure 4-1. Proportion of cases reported by age category for 2000-2016.

Figure 4-2. Age and sex distribution of total laboratory reports counts of non-typhoidal Salmonella in England and Wales between 2000 and 2016.

4.2 Serotypes predominance

A total of 674 different serotypes were identified in the data set for the years 2000-2016, with the most common being:

1. *S. Enteritidis* (51.46% of the serotypes identified)
2. *S. Typhimurium* (18.08% of the serotypes identified)
3. *S. Newport* (1.84% of the serotypes identified)

It is worth noting that the remaining serotypes accounting for approximately one fourth of the cases (28.62%) correspond to less predominant species, including serotypes categorised as "unnamed" and "other". This substantial amount emphasizes the great variety of circulating *Salmonella* serotypes. The unknown serotypes (4.62% of the of the serotypes reported) were included in the analysis. For a more detailed overview of the most common serotypes over time, see Figure 4-3. I conclude that:

- *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* were the predominant known serotypes for all years.
- The third most common serotype varied over time, with *S. Virchow* being relatively dominant until 2009. From 2011 onwards, *S. Newport* and *S. Infantis* were virtually tied for third place.
- There is a wide variety of non-predominant serotypes that, when combined, can cause a considerable number of disease events, sometimes even surpassing the number of cases caused by *S. Typhimurium*).

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Figure 4-3. NTS serotype predominance over the years 1989-2020. *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* remained at the top two every year. In grey, unnamed serotypes or categorised as “other”.

4.3 Reporting day bias

A reporting bias was identified coinciding with days of the week (Figure 4-4) or the year (Figure 4-5) when surveillance or care-seeking patterns were reduced, and the consequent compensatory effect of increased cases reported after a holiday season. Two non-exclusive strategies were considered to correct for uneven reporting patterns: a 7-day centered moving average for the weekend bias, and a 3-day rolling average paired with the function “holidayLONDON” from the “timeDate” R package (Wuertz et al., 2022) for accounting for bank holidays in England¹⁴. The reporting bias was initially corrected by calculating the mean cases rolled from the three days prior and after the specimen date for every week and bank holidays. Other smoothing techniques and time windows were explored (See Appendix B). However, the discontinuity of reported cases in the time series, indicative of underreporting linked to holiday periods, persisted after smoothing. This highlighted the inadequacy of using a moving average to correct for such underreporting. To avoid over-manipulating the data, I finally decided to not correct for this reporting day bias. This decision was substantiated by

¹⁴ The 8 bank holidays in England each year are: New Year's Day, Good Friday, Easter Monday, Spring (May), Last Monday of May, End of Summer (Last Monday) August, Christmas Eve, Christmas Day). Other type of holiday, such as school mid-term, were not considered due to its variable nature.

Results of a descriptive exploration of reported salmonellosis cases the fact that the day-of-reporting effect was, at least in part, automatically corrected when the incubation period and reporting delays were eliminated. Additionally, averaging the weather values seven days prior to the specimen date intended to capture the weather conditions surrounding the reporting timeframe, including holiday periods.

Figure 4-4: Day of the week when cases were reported for the study period (2000-2016).

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Figure 4-5. Smoothing effect of the 7-day window simple moving average (SMA) of the reporting date for an interval of 2 years during the study period of 2000-2026 for demonstrative purposes. Note the occasional reporting troughs compatible with holiday periods, followed by subsequent compensatory increase in cases reported.

4.4 Seasonality of reported cases

A seasonal pattern of cases reported becomes evident between July and September when displaying all the cases combined for all the years (Figure 3-3). Given the fluctuating total number of reported cases over the years, which can be attributed to the advancement of diagnostic techniques and public health strategies, I aimed to evaluate any potential changes in the seasonality patterns. To this end, I performed a wavelet analysis using the WaveletComp version 1.1 package in R (Roesch & Schmidbauer, 2018). Wavelet analysis is an appealing method to visually explore the dependencies between two signals (Cazelles et al., 2007), such as the relationship between time and incidence in this context. This type of analysis is useful for identifying periodic patterns of disease in a time series difficult to detect by visualization of the time series, including frequency changes in time or overlapping periods (Cazelles et al., 2008; Rösch & Schmidbauer, 2016). For instance, wavelet analysis detected a change in the frequency of measles cases in London, which was evidenced by a reduced periodicity of annual cases following vaccination in the 1970's (Grenfell et al., 2001).

A main signal was identified in the wavelet power spectrum analysis for a period at about 360 days across all years, confirming that there was no significant change in the annual seasonal pattern of reported salmonellosis (Figure 4-6, Figure 4-7). This is consistent with the annual incidence pattern observed both in the complete dataset (1989-2020, Figure 3-2), and the power spectrum averaged over all years (Figure 3-3). Additionally, other smaller signals were identifiable at the beginning of the time series, with frequencies of 6 months (187 days) and 7 days, coinciding with the weekend report bias. The gradual disappearance of these signals after the year 2006 is inferred, potentially reflecting a change in reporting patterns. This was confirmed by a detailed breakdown of all the signals composing the overall seasonal incidence pattern for the entire time series (Figure 4-8). Between 2007 and 2010, four National Control Programmes (NCP) for the control of *Salmonella* with specific seroprevalence reduction targets were implemented in layer and breeding flocks in the UK (Defra, 2007, 2009). Its success may be related to the progressive extinction of some signals. Given that the overall periodicity of cases reported between 2000 and 2016 does not change considerably, the principles of the conditional incidence analysis are considered adequate, as it is based on aggregating all the years studied. This is further explored in the next chapter, as the trend in the number cases reported is taken into account.

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Figure 4-6. Wavelet power spectrum of salmonellosis cases reported between 2000-2016 after correction for incubation and reporting delays. It outlines the power of the signal (gradient colour) as a function of its period (or inverse frequency) (Y axis) in time (X axis) as a measure of the strength and occurrence of signals present in the time series. High wavelet coefficients (red colour and black line) reveal stronger seasonal patterns across the years studied for 360, 187 and 7 days. The main annual pattern of reported salmonellosis cases is present across all years. The shaded areas at the top corners identify the region subjected to errors arising from dealing with a finite-length time series (edge effect).

Figure 4-7. Visualization of the patterns observed in the wavelet colour spectrum after averaging the power over the entire temporal domain. The solid circles indicate that the respective period is significant at the 5% level. The intensity of each signal is comparable, with the annual signal being the strongest, followed by the signal occurring every six months.

Detrended, Rescaled, Time-Series of Salmonellosis Cases

Figure 4-8. Decomposition of the different signals conforming the observed pattern of the seasonal cases reported (Original, top row). The signals present a variation in intensity over time, especially after the year 2006, with the annual and 6 months signals gotten slightly flattened, and the 2.6 months disappearing to reappear sporadically from 2009. The signals under the category of “other” are compatible with the weekly and holiday reporting bias, which is variable and does not seem a fixed pattern. Note that the waves are rescaled to enable comparison of different magnitudes.

4.5 Detrending the time series

The wavelet analysis showed that changes in the seasonal patterns (*i.e.*, frequency) of salmonellosis are negligible. However, a difference in the number of cases reported over the 17 years selected for study is maintained, exhibiting a consistent downward trend from 2000 onwards (Upper Figure 4-7). The origin of this trend is unclear, but changes in human behavior, diagnostic and reporting procedures, and public health interventions are believed to play a significant role in contributing to this trend. Despite its uncertain origin, removing this “external” component from our data (*i.e.*, detrending) helped to emphasize the seasonal pattern of interest (Lower Figure 4-9). Depending on the characteristics of the data, detrending the reported cases using the mean of the cases can potentially improve predictions while, correcting for reporting bias as well as the human behaviour and other unknown factors influencing the number of cases reported (Dessavre et al., 2019). Thus, I propose the detrended time series to be a more accurate representation of the epidemiology of salmonellosis driven by the underlying bio-physical process causing disease while reducing the effects of changes in human influence.

The “detrended cases” produce a seasonal time series where the overall average is set to one (Figure 4-9). To give a meaningful dimension to the salmonellosis estimates, the detrended time series were multiplied by the average annual number of cases reported over the last 5 years, so that the most recent human behavior, diagnostic procedures and latest public health strategies were incorporated in the results. The multiplier was 15 cases for the years 2011-2016 reported in England and Wales.

The R package “dplr” version 1.7.4. (Bunn et al., 2022; Bunn, 2008, 2010) was used to detrend the cases with the spline method, which were then used to calculate the conditional incidence of the selected weather parameters. A comparison of the performance of both detrended and non-detrended timeseries is shown in Chapter 5. See Appendix A for the conditional incidence identifying differences of the effect of weather for the different year intervals where the magnitude of the recorded cases was different.

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Figure 4-9. Visual representation of detrending the time series data aimed for removing the downtrend of the cases. Upper: cases reported from 1989 to 2016. Lower: detrended cases showcasing the shape of cases.

Chapter 5

The Conditional Incidence in England and Wales

5.1 Context

There is a shared consensus and a large body of evidence about the association of weather and climate with the transmission and dissemination of diseases (Colston et al., 2022; Mora et al., 2022). For example, in the case of vector-borne diseases like dengue or malaria, climatic conditions can impact the life cycle of mosquito vectors and the replication of pathogens within them. Additionally, certain respiratory droplet-transmitted diseases, such as influenza, may exhibit seasonal patterns associated with changes in temperature and humidity. Understanding the influence of weather on diseases is essential for developing effective prevention and control strategies.

The objective of this chapter is to investigate the specific impact of weather on salmonellosis, recognizing that weather plays an important role in its seasonal dynamics among other concurrent factors. The motivation of this research question is based on the recognition that *Salmonella* exhibits sensitivity to variations in temperature, precipitation, and other meteorological parameters. The influence of weather on diseases such as salmonellosis may seem obvious given the well-known relevance of temperature for its replication. However, weather conceived as the result of a complex and simultaneous interaction of physical components, renders its overall influence less evident. This includes the potential effect of weather on human behaviour. As such, a deeper exploration into the impact of weather on the prevalence of salmonellosis may shed light on non-obvious patterns, risk factors, and potential avenues for preventive interventions.

In this chapter, nine raw (*i.e.*, maximum and mean air temperature, dewpoint temperature, surface air pressure, relative humidity, mean precipitation, sunshine duration, wind speed,

The Conditional Incidence in England and Wales

global radiation) and five calculated weather factors (*i.e.*, day length, temperature amplitude, and indoor comfort temperature and relative humidity) were explored in different combinations. These factors were selected for their potential to modulate bacterial proliferation in food, *i.e.*, effect of warmth, water condensation, water permeability and microcidal effect of UV-C radiation (Refer to Chapter 3.1.3 for further information). Based on previous work (Lo Iacono et al., 2024), the weather factors were assessed in sets of three through a stratification process, moving from factors with broader to narrower values. This approach aimed to capture as many three-way combinations as possible. For example, the range of temperature was consistently broader than relative humidity, which in turn was wider than day length, indicating the order of stratification as temperature, humidity, daylength. The intention was to understand the complexity of the interrelationship between several meteorological factors without generating overly intricate results.

The results of applying the statistical approach in England and Wales are shown in this chapter. Refer to Chapter 3.2.2 for a detailed explanation of the method. Briefly, the conditional incidence model was fed with 17 years of incidence data from England and Wales, assuming a relatively constant behavioural patterns, such as frequency of medical visits, food preferences and the absence of significant changes in surveillance and control strategies that would lead to variations in the case-reporting rate. This assumption is supported by results from the wavelet analysis, showing no sensible change in the frequency patterns, and by removing the trend from the data. Cases predicted by the model were obtained by multiplying the number of residents of a catchment area by the probability of salmonellosis corresponding to the weather conditions of each day in each area (namely, reconstruction of the time series). The calculation of predicted incidence of salmonellosis was based on surveillance data and the weather conditions at the likely day of infection of each instance (refer to Chapter 4.5 for further explanation of detrending and rescaling reported cases).. The model estimates the incidence of the disease conditioned to specific weather factors irrespective of time or place of occurrence.

The adequacy of the model was assessed visually by comparing the predicted outcomes with empirical observed cases. Different combinations of weather factors were assessed by comparing the cases reconstructed with the model with historical incidence. Given the large

number of possible combinations, a selection of suitable and non-suitable combinations is presented and discussed in the main text to illustrate the variability of results when considering different weather factors. The rest of the combinations explored are presented in the Appendix E. It is suggested to compare the outcomes of the conditional incidence in this chapter with the variability of weather factors analysed in Chapter 3.1.3. The open-source code is available at: [https://github.com/lauracris-7/Conditional Incidence Salmonella/tree/main](https://github.com/lauracris-7/Conditional_Incidence_Salmonella/tree/main).

5.2 Incidence conditional to weather factors and reconstruction of the time series

A visual representation of the resulting expected number of cases compared to the historical reported data serves to evaluate the model's performance and assessing the suitability of the weather factors of election (Figure 5-1). A comparison between the analysis performed with detrended and raw cases is provided. It is worth noting the reduction in both the magnitude and uncertainty of the detrended cases when compared to the raw case data. This is because the detrending process intentionally removes the trend from the time series, which is typically a change in the mean over time (Figure 5-1 B). The uncertainty associated with the detrended cases captures the variability of cases reported in England and Wales over the most recent five years of surveillance data available.

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Figure 5-1. Reconstruction of estimated and daily laboratory-confirmed cases across all locations, country-wide and averaged for all years studied. In red the laboratory-confirmed cases reported to UKHSA for 2000-2016; in turquoise the cases reconstructed by the model for the same years conditional to **dewpoint temperature-mean precipitation-day length** (A) and the same variables with the adjusted reported (detrended and rescaled) cases (B). The bold line corresponds to the mean cases modelled/reported for the years studied, and the ribbon to the 25 and 75 quantiles, representing the inter-annual variability across all the years studied.

A notable visual correspondence can be observed between the model's performance and the laboratory-confirmed adjusted reported cases when considering the effects of dewpoint temperature, precipitation and day length (Figure 5-2). Note the model capturing the overall inter-annual variability with only minor discrepancies. Interestingly, this degree of agreement with the data was not observed for campylobacteriosis (Lo Iacono et al., 2024), nor did it occur for every combination of weather factors that were examined (Table 5-1 and related discussion). It is worth noting that the reconstruction plots (Figure 5-1 and similar) display only the number of salmonellosis cases. The non-cases (the *zeros*) can be simply estimated from the difference between the total number of residents in each catchment areas and the cases. For instance, the annual number of cases in the catchment area corresponding to the postcode GU167UJ for the year 2016 was 98 compared to the 813,603 non-cases, corresponding to a percentage of 0.012%. This large excess of zeros naturally arises from our approach without the need to explicitly model the system as Zero-Inflated Models.

Figure 5-2. Reconstruction of the time series of adjusted reported (yellow) and modelled cases (green) for the years studied conditional to mean dewpoint temperature, mean precipitation and day length. The close performance of the model with respect to the empirical cases can be observed in detail for each year.

The visual harmony of the simulations with empirical data confirmed the **suitability of the conditional incidence approach** of using a combination of weather factors to adequately estimate both the inter-annual and intra-annual risk of salmonellosis. Moreover, several factors were identified as relevant for reproducing salmonellosis incidence, namely **mean and maximum air temperature, dewpoint temperature, relative humidity, precipitation, and global radiation** (Figure 5-3). Day length proved to be a good proxy for global radiation, in addition to not being affected by stochastic noise since it is deterministically determined by latitude and the day of the year. Other less suitable weather factors included temperature amplitude, surface air pressure, wind speed, and sunshine duration. Refer to Appendix E: Reconstruction of all weather factors tested: Figure E-1 to E-5 for a visual evaluation; and Table 5-1 for a summary of findings. The analysis when considering typical indoor environmental conditions (*i.e.*, comfortable temperature and humidity levels in an enclosed space, the place where infections most frequently occur (Schweizer et al., 2007)) did not lead to a notable improvement of the results as compared with outdoor weather values (Supplementary Figure E-5). Averaged weather values over a time lag of 7, 14, 30 and 60 days were explored with no evident improvement of results (Supplementary Figure F-1). Given the qualitatively similar results, a time lag of 7 days was chosen in line with the findings of (Kovats et al., 2004).

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Weather factor	Agreement of the model with empirical data	Relevant combination tested	Figure
Maximum air temperature (Tmax)	High	Temp*-Precip-DL Temp-RH-DL	Figure E-1 Figure E-2 Figure E-3
Mean air temperature (Tmean)	High		
Mean dewpoint temperature (Tdew)	High		
Mean/Cumulative precipitation (Precip)	High		
Relative humidity (RH)	High		
Day length (DL)	High		
Global radiation (GR)	Average	Temp-Precip-GR Temp-RH-GR	
Indoor conditions	High	Tmean-RH-DL	Figure E-5 (6)
Mean wind speed (Wind)	Average/variable	Tdew-Wind-DL Tmean-Wind-DL	Figure E-5 (1-5)
Temperature amplitude (Tamp)	Low		Figure E-4
Mean surface air pressure (Pair)	Low		Figure E-1 (3, 7, 11) Figure E-2 (3, 7, 11) Figure E-3 (3, 5, 8, 13) Figure E-4 (3, 7, 11) Figure E-5 (3)
Sunshine duration (Sun)	Low		Figure E-1 (4, 8, 12) Figure E-2 (4, 8, 12) Figure E-3 (4, 9, 14) Figure E-4 (4, 8, 12)

Table 5-1. Performance of weather combinations tested. *Temp comprises mean, maximum air and dewpoint temperature.

Figure 5-3. Continued on next page.

The Conditional Incidence in England and Wales

Figure 5-3. Reconstruction of averaged modelled and laboratory-confirmed adjusted reported cases at country level, conditional to different combinations of weather factors. **Left:** full time series. **Right:** all years averaged together. These are representative samples illustrating the predictions of the model for different weather factors in a favourable (A, B, C) and less favourable combination (D) when compared with empirical data. A) Maximum air temperature, mean precipitation, global radiation. B) Mean dewpoint temperature, relative humidity, day length. C) Mean air temperature, wind speed, day length. D) Dewpoint temperature, surface air pressure, precipitation. The absence of available air pressure records for the year 2000 and part of 2002 did not allow the model to make any prediction in these instances.

According to the graphs depicting both averaged and full time series reconstruction (Figure 5-3 for a diverse selection of weather combinations, and Appendix E for all the combinations considered), the combination of mean air temperature, relative humidity and day length was selected as suitable to derive the conditional incidence. Other combinations including dewpoint temperature and precipitation were also appropriate, with the choice of weather factors depending ultimately on data availability.

The influence of different weather factors on the risk of salmonellosis is not additive nor linear, but depends on the interactions between them. Therefore, a meticulous and careful interpretation is necessary to fully understand their isolated impact on the incidence of salmonellosis conditioned to specific weather factors (Figure 5-4 and supplementary Figure E-9). All weather combinations consistently displayed an initial stationary period of minimal change in salmonellosis risk, followed by a linear upward rise. The resulting graph has a sigmoidal or a hockey-stick shaped curve, depending on the amount of data available. This is especially evident with day length lasting 12-15 hours, and less clear for both shortest and longest day length. The threshold for this turning point from the stationary to the linear phase varies with the weather factor combination considered. Typically, it falls within the range of 7 to 13 °C for dewpoint, mean and maximum air temperature, in increasing order. Higher risk was observed for values of global radiation between 3,696-15,294 kJ/m² and maximum temperatures above 10°C, which typically corresponds to the months of April to June, and July to October (see together with Figure 3-9, Page 36 and Supplementary Figure E-9 G). The duration of the days during these months is 12-15 hours, which is consistent with the results obtained when using day length as a proxy (Figure 5-4). In fact, an increase of 11% in salmonellosis incidence per 1°C increase was found for mean daily temperatures greater than 10°C in the months of April to June and July to October (12-15 hours long) (Supplementary Figure E-9 E, G). Higher degree of overlap of the different profiles in the conditional incidence graphs (including the shaded area representing 95% confidence interval) indicates that the factors in question are not expected to be the true explanatory variables. The profiles of different values of precipitation and relative humidity in general can be differentiated. However, the high degree of overlap for short day length (< 9h) suggests that a relevant effect over salmonellosis exists only for longer days (Figure 5-4 and Supplementary Figure E-9 A, C, D, F, G and H). This feature was also observed for campylobacteriosis (Lo Iacono et al., 2024).

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Slightly lower risk was identified for drier conditions at higher temperatures when days are the longest (greater than 15 hours-long, corresponding to the months of June and July), and higher risk for the same weather conditions for 9 to 15 hours of day duration (typically March to May and mid-August to October). This variable risk upon different day lengths goes unnoticed if assessing the influence of day length alone, which flattens from 12 hours onwards (Supplementary Figure E-8).

Figure 5-4. Number of modelled salmonellosis cases per 10 million inhabitants (Y axis) based on the combined effect of mean air temperature (X axis), relative humidity and day length. Data are divided in quantiles ensuring the same number of observations for each bin. The coloured bands indicate a range for relative humidity, with the ribbon displaying the 25th and 75th percentile as measure of the associated uncertainty. Compare with reconstruction plot in Supplementary Figure E-2 (9), where modelled and empirical cases are similar.

Salmonellosis incidence data at diagnostic laboratory locations were spatially assigned to one of the 15 correspondent PHE centre regions using QGIS ([QGIS Desktop version 3.16 "Hannover"](#)) (Figure 5-5). Data on land use, animal census distribution, and farming land were obtained from a combination of open and private repositories from Defra at yearly resolution. However, these spatial factors were not included in the analysis due to insufficient temporal and spatial resolution of the data. We also explicitly tested the model predictions of daily number of cases per catchment area using the conditional incidence for a suitable weather factors combination (*i.e.*, mean air temperature, mean precipitation and day length), and a lag of 7 days. The spatial analysis presented in Figure 5-5 shows the capability of the approach to capture, at least in part, the spatial variability of salmonellosis arising from spatial variability in the weather factors.

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Figure 5-5. Spatial performance of the model averaged per catchment area for 2000-2016. **Top:** scatter plot representing the sum of all cases modelled (X axis) and reported (Y axis) at every location. **Bottom:** Spatial location of the logarithmic average modelled cases (blue squares) compared to the empirical cases (red circles). The size of the points is proportional to the number of observations.

5.3 Discussion

The model developed in this thesis describes the effect that weather has in salmonellosis incidence conditional to specific weather factors by 1) identifying and characterising the weather factors associated with salmonellosis incidence, and (2) testing the suitability of using weather data to estimate the risk of salmonellosis. The approach is applicable when long-term, high-resolution surveillance data is available. For an accurate study of the effect of weather on salmonellosis, the approach would ideally analyse actual infection rates rather than reported incidence. However, due to the nature of the data analysed, conclusions were based on reported data, whose patterns were assumed to not be significantly affected by weather factors. In other words, the weather conditions would not interfere in the reporting habits of patients or diagnostic laboratories across the country. On another hand, the different weather factors are highly inter-connected whose single effect is difficult to isolate. Therefore, the novelty of this study lies in the comprehensive exploration of the effect of 14 weather factors at high spatio-temporal linkage, stratified in different combinations, which challenges other studies of single parameters in a silo (Britton et al., 2010; Cherrie et al., 2018; Stephen & Barnett, 2016).

The reconstruction of the time series obtained by incorporating relevant weather factors in the model, effectively replicated the primary peak of salmonellosis incidence observed in England and Wales during the months of August and September. Furthermore, it accurately captured the observed inter-annual variability as the time series across all years shows in detail (Figure 5-2, Figure 5-3 left side). The agreement with empirical data for the inter-annual variability captured by the model is superior to the findings of the model when applied to campylobacteriosis (Lo Iacono et al., 2024), suggesting a stronger and/or exhaustive association of the chosen weather factors in *Salmonella* as compared to *Campylobacter*. This is a further **validation of the methodology** presented in Chapter 3, corroborating an agent-based model simulated by (Lo Iacono et al., 2024), and a confirmation of the strong association of weather on salmonellosis disease. By visual comparison of model predictions with empirical data, a set of **weather factor combinations** with a relevant influence on the incidence of salmonellosis were identified and their effect was characterized.

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A visual assessment was conducted to analyse the model's outputs and identify an array of weather combinations suitable for assessing the risk of infection. The purpose of reconstructing historical cases under the influence of various weather combinations was to identify suitable combinations of weather factors associated with salmonellosis. The minor differences observed in the reconstruction plots of different weather combinations did not provide sufficient justification for selecting one specific combination over the others. Some metrics could be used, such as root mean square of the sum of the differences between predictions and observation. However, ranking weather combinations was avoided given the variability introduced by the stochastic elements present in the methodology, such as the size of bins for classifying the weather factors, time lag, or the available incubation period based on the most commonly reported serotype. These sources of stochasticity could slightly alter the results, making it challenging to favour one combination over another on the basis on a single metric. A rigorous analysis based on propagation of errors (*e.g.*, (Bevington et al., 1993)) and a systematic sensitivity analysis was beyond the scope of this work and recommended for future work. Predictions of the model for some other weather factors (temperature amplitude, surface air pressure, wind speed, and sunshine duration) exhibited limited agreement with empirical data, allowing to narrow down the pool of potential weather factors combinations associated with salmonellosis. The results of the model for indoor environment conditions revealed that outdoor weather values yield better results of the conditional incidence model, despite food being most commonly consumed indoors.

Maximum and mean air temperature, dewpoint temperature, precipitation, relative humidity and day length were some of the weather factors with an adequate association with historical salmonellosis records. These findings are consistent with previous studies that identified a notable association between salmonellosis and temperature (Bentham & Langford, 2001; Cherrie et al., 2018; Fisman, 2007; Kovats et al., 2004; Lake et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2018; Spector & Kenyon, 2012), although the influence of other concomitant weather variables is less obvious (Wang et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2014). Predictions obtained from the combination of mean air temperature, relative humidity and day length exhibited a close agreement with empirical data. Other variables less commonly studied include snowfall, wind speed, duration of sunshine, insolation, cloudiness and vapour pressure (Cherrie et al., 2018; Park et al., 2018). At the same time, factors of difficult quantification that were not accounted in the analysis

(such as human behaviour or other environmental factors), could have a decisive role in infection.

The model allows to estimate salmonellosis notifications based on weather forecast. However, the **main contribution of the analysis** lies in its ability to provide detailed insight into the various weather interactions and their connection to salmonellosis incidence. The reciprocal influence of the factors on each other reveals that, in effect, the influence of the different weather factors is not necessarily linear or additive, as observed in the conditional incidence charts. Indeed, temperature is positioned as a relevant factor driving salmonellosis. When assessing the single effect of mean air temperature (Supplementary Figure E-7), the effect it exerts in the probability of finding a salmonellosis case follows a smooth sigmoidal curve. This probability increases exponentially above 9°C, reflecting the ability of salmonella to grow at a higher rate above this temperature. However, when evaluating the impact of mean air temperature in conjunction with two (Supplementary Figures E-6) or three other weather factors (Figure 5-4), the effect becomes more complex: a lower risk was observed for days longer than 15 hours, and a variable risk at lower levels of relative humidity. Same applies when assessing the isolated effect of day length. Day length was chosen because it could be a proxy for ultra-violet radiation, which is expected to reduce the survival of salmonella in the environment (Gayán et al., 2012). However, no reduction in incidence was observed with increasing day length. A possible explanation is that day length is a proxy for the time of the year and the association with day length reflect change in population behaviour during the year. The current contribution to the existing knowledge on *Salmonella* already provides an insight into the mechanism of seasonality underlying the final reporting of cases, such as population behaviour and environmental effects on host and pathogen (Fisman, 2007). Further research, however, is required especially on the nature of the association with day length. An example of how the conditional incidence can assist in gaining an insight of the mechanism is provided in Chapter 8, where the theoretical conditional incidence arising from microbial growth in food is compared with observed conditional incidence. This knowledge is essential for disease preparedness and prevention, especially with regard to the increasing anthropogenic impact on the environment and climate change.

Chapter 6

Application of the conditional incidence model in the Netherlands

6.1 Context

The basis of the conditional incidence model is to capture how the weather is associated with salmonellosis incidence without fitting any data. The association can arise from multiple factors, including *universal* biological casues (*e.g.*, the survival of bacteria in the environment) and human behaviour, which can depend on the specific spatio-temporal situation under study. Hence, it is not obvious whether the shape of the conditional incidence is universal, and therefore generalizable to other spatio-temporal scenarios, or rather specific to the situation in England and Wales. Our descriptive analysis, however, showed that the patterns of the seasonality in salmonellosis incidence do not significantly depend on time. Therefore, the effect of weather on salmonellosis identified in England and Wales is suggested to be constant, irrespective of the location of the patient in England and Wales. Here, the applicability of the conditional incidence to other countries is explored.

In this chapter, the conditional incidence model developed from reported data in England and Wales in Chapter 5 is applied to the Netherlands. The open-source code is available at:

https://github.com/lauracris-7/Conditional_Incidence_Salmonella/tree/main

The data and scientific expertise presented in this chapter are the result of a fruitful collaboration with the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment in the Netherlands (RIVM). This collaboration was made possible by a travel grant from the STM-OHEJP, which facilitated a research visit to the Netherlands (Utrecht) spanning from April to May 2022 and a joint publication (subject to submission).

6.2 Adjustment of the methodology to the Netherlands

6.2.1 Data and data harmonization

Incidence data included daily cases reported to the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment in the Netherlands (RIVM) during 2015-2019. The year 2016 was not included in the analysis due to a disproportionately higher observed cases linked to a country-wide outbreak (Pijnacker et al., 2019). At the same time, the year 2020 was dismissed due to the reporting singularity linked to the COVID-19 pandemic (EFSA and ECDC, 2021b). The rest of the outbreak data were kept, including as much case information as possible to test the model.

Serotypes of non-foodborne interest were removed to match the cases used to build the model. In both countries, a case was culture-confirmed by a diagnostic laboratory, with the difference that in England and Wales notification of non-typhoid salmonellosis is mandatory (UKHSA, 2022) while in the Netherlands is voluntary (Chanamé Pinedo et al., 2022). Surveillance of salmonellosis cases relies on medical doctors and laboratories to notify suspected and confirmed cases. Further details regarding surveillance and diagnostic methods have been published elsewhere for the UK (Wheeler et al., 1999) and the Netherlands (Chanamé Pinedo et al., 2022). The reported cases were filtered by selecting *Salmonella* subspecies of foodborne interest (*i.e.*, *Salmonella sp. enterica ssp. enterica.*) and excluding cases with confirmed travel history or unknown patient residence. Where a same patient was re-assessed for an on-going salmonellosis diagnosis, only the first recorded instance was accounted for in a 3-month window. The reporting delays were adapted to the Netherlands as follows: time to healthcare 0-3 days for blood samples, and 7-11 for stool samples, sample delay 0-2 days. An additional delay was included for the time for a sample to get to the RIVM (1-2 days for blood, and 1-3 for stool samples). The delays were drawn from a log-normal distribution, from available estimates (Bonačić Marinović et al., 2015; CDC, 2015) and expert opinion from collaborators from the RIVM (Mughini-Gras and Pijnacker personal communication).

Salmonellosis incidence data were linked to the combination of mean air temperature, relative humidity and day length for consistency with Chapter 5. The weather data were downloaded from the Netherlands Royal Meteorological Institute open-source platform

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(KNMI: <https://www.knmi.nl/klimaat>). The residents' information was downloaded from Statistics Netherlands (CBS: <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb>) at full 6-digit postal code level (*i.e.*, PC6). This high-resolution post code is equivalent to the resolution used in England and Wales. All the data were harmonised at a 5km grid resolution. Values at both upper and lower ends of weather registered in the Netherlands that had no corresponding matching record in the UK were removed from the analysis. This implied that 2.5% of the total Dutch weather data had an undetermined conditional incidence. To overcome the difference in size of the countries and trends in case-reporting inherent in each country, the conditional incidence was rescaled by multiplying the detrended conditional incidence for England and Wales by a coefficient representative of the burden of salmonellosis in the Netherlands situation. This was set equal to the product of i) the annual average of reported cases of salmonellosis in the Netherlands, and ii) the ratio of the population size of the Netherlands vs the population of England and Wales (as of year 2019). The first term takes into account the idiosyncrasies of the specific country (*e.g.*, reporting patterns), while the second term was necessary to correct for the fact that number of catchments in England and Wales (where the conditional incidence is calculated) is higher, and of different size and density of population, compared to ones of the Netherlands.

6.3 Results

6.3.1 Descriptive exploration of Dutch data

A total of 3,231 cases were included in the study. An exploratory analysis of the data for the years of study identified the highest incidence in young patients between 5-29 years-old, as opposed to a younger age group found in the UK (0-4 years-old). The distribution of cases by sex was equal in the Netherlands, as in England and Wales.

Regarding the prevalence of the *Salmonella* serotypes, a comparative of the three most common serovars in both countries for the years are summarised in Table 6-1. The most prevalent serotypes coincided, although in different proportion. When combining monophasic Typhimurium and Typhimurium serotypes (as categorized in the UK), *S.* Typhimurium (40.98%) exhibited a higher prevalence than *S.* Enteritidis in the Netherlands.

England and Wales (2000-2016) n= 144,703 The Netherlands (2004-2019) n=XX

S. Enteritidis (51.46%)	S. Enteritidis (28.93%)
S. Typhimurium (including monophasic variant) (18.08%)	S. Typhimurium (27.48%)
S. Newport (1.84%)	S. monophasic Typhimurium (12.92%)

Table 6-1. Comparative of the most commonly laboratory-confirmed Salmonella serotypes in England and Wales and in the Netherlands.

6.3.2 Outcomes of the model applied in the Netherlands

The conditional incidence built from long-term surveillance data from England and Wales and weather data in the Netherlands, were used to infer salmonellosis cases from the Netherlands and compare to their reported numbers. The model captured a close match between simulated and historical cases when applied to surveillance data from the Netherlands (Figure 6-1). The cases reconstructed with the model broadly captured the salmonellosis incidence recorded in the Netherlands. The primary summer peak of incidence was identified, with minor discrepancies observed in June, July and October (Figure 6-2).

Figure 6-1. Time series of the reconstruction of daily cases produced by the model (green) compared to the empirical reported cases in the Netherlands (yellow).

Application of the conditional incidence model in the Netherlands

Figure 6-2. Reconstruction of the average number of cases across the Netherlands at a daily resolution. In red the reported cases to RIVM for 2015, 2017-2019 averaged for all locations; in turquoise the cases reconstructed for the same years with the model based on UK data conditional to mean air temperature, relative humidity and day length. The shaded area represents the 25% and 75% quantiles.

6.4 Discussion

Despite the implementation of control strategies aimed at reducing the burden of *Salmonella*, such as enhanced biosecurity measures and vaccination plans, salmonellosis continues to cause a substantial burden on societies in many countries, including the Netherlands. Improper animal and food handling, as well as environmental contamination and persistence, are considered to be the main reasons for the difficult eradication of this persistent infection (Oastler et al., 2019). The number of cases is known to be under-reported, with the community cases estimated to be 3.2 (95% CI: 1.4-12.0) times more than what is reported to national authorities in England (Wheeler et al., 1999), and 14 (5-95% quartiles: 3.6-56) in the Netherlands (Kemmeren et al., 2006).

In the previous chapter, the effect of 6 weather factors in different combinations was found to have a relevant association with human salmonellosis incidence. The simultaneous effect of mean air temperature, relative humidity and day length is one of the combinations seen to have a driving effect in human salmonellosis, among other suitable combinations. This is in line with previous studies that pointed at the effect of temperature (Bentham & Langford, 2001; Cherrie et al., 2018; Fisman, 2007; Kovats et al., 2004; Lake et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2018; Spector & Kenyon, 2012), humidity (Xu et al., 2014) or rainfall (Wang et al., 2018) as important

Application of the conditional incidence model in the Netherlands determinants of salmonellosis. All these studies identify a positive association between salmonellosis and temperature, being the influence of the other weather variables less clear.

The accurate reconstruction of the patterns of salmonellosis incidence in the Netherlands, based on epidemiology data from England and Wales, supports the hypothesis that the way the weather influences salmonellosis incidence, (*i.e.*, the shape of the conditional incidence described in Chapter 5) is not limited to a specific geographical location. However, the model's performance exhibits marginal discrepancies when applied in a different country, highlighting inherent surveillance data bias. This bias includes social factors like reporting patterns and patient health-seeking behaviours, as well as location-specific characteristics of salmonellosis infections, such as serotype predominance and their different susceptibility to weather, and proportion of susceptible populations. Furthermore, the model could be adjusted with a factor that accounts for the disease burden and specific population size of each location. At the same time, assessing the model's performance over longer surveillance periods would facilitate a more accurate evaluation by reducing reconstruction plot noise.

The influence of weather on seasonal incidence of salmonellosis is suggested to have a universal effect that offsets the specific reporting patterns of each country. By adjusting certain parameters, like reporting delay and incubation period, the model could be applicable to other infectious diseases or countries when long-term surveillance data are available. The model was applied in the Netherlands, a country with a temperate climate similar to the UK. The application of the model to countries with diverse weather conditions, such as tropical countries or those in the southern hemisphere, would provide stronger evidence and insights. This was left for future research.

Chapter 7

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5

7.1 Context

As discussed in Chapter 2.2.2, *Salmonella* is highly influenced by weather variability. In Chapter 5, a relevant association between salmonellosis and weather factors was confirmed, in particular temperature and precipitation. Building on this finding, Chapter 6 confirmed the applicability of the conditional incidence to a different scenario, and potentially different climates. Understanding the impact of climate change on the magnitude and temporal distribution of salmonellosis and other concurrent diseases would enhance preparedness and the efficient allocation of medical resources. In this chapter, the expected incidence of salmonellosis in the scenario of current climate projections is explored, provided this conditional incidence identified holds the same driving force in *Salmonella* in the near future.

Maximum air temperature, precipitation and day length were the weather factors used for this analysis. This decision was made based on the relevant associations found with salmonellosis in Chapter 5, as well as to showcase the versatility of the model in handling another combination of relevant weather factors different from those discussed in the previous chapters. Moreover, some weather factors are not available in the climate projections database (Met Office Hadley Centre, 2018), such as global radiation. Precipitation is a commonly studied in the field of climate change and shows less daily variation as compared to relative humidity, which is associated with lower uncertainties when applying the model. At the same time, day length is a calculated physical parameter that is not affected by the measuring methodology nor measuring errors.

The UK Climate Projections (UKCP18) provide an updated range of climate change projections dated in 2018 (Murphy et al., 2019). Simulations from the Met Office Hadley Centre model

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and other models developed across the world were used to produce a range of possible climate futures. The various climate models or “members” were run with different configurations and physical parameters to capture the range of uncertainties for possible future climate scenarios. These models were run for four greenhouse gas concentration scenarios (Representative Concentration Pathway, RCP) encompassing a range of greenhouse emissions in the coming years. From these, RCP 8.5¹⁵ is the highest CO₂ emissions scenario in which no mitigation measures are set in place. This scenario was chosen for this chapter following a conservative approach, as this worst-case scenario is still possible although less likely (Bernie et al., 2018; IPCC, 2021; Riahi et al., 2011).

7.2 Adjustment of the methodology to the climate change projections

7.2.1 Projected data: climate and population up to 2043

Daily land projections at a 60km-grid resolution were downloaded for the 15 members or climate projections generated by the global climate model HadGEM3-GC3.05 (Met Office Hadley Centre, 2018) for the RCP 8.5 scenario. Data are available at <http://data.ceda.ac.uk/badc/ukcp18/data/land-rcm/uk/country/rcp85/>³. The “ncdf4” package for R version 4.2.2 (Pierce, 2022) was used to extract climate data in NetCDF format. For computational convenience, the discontinuous years 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040 and 2043 were analysed to provide an overview of the change in salmonellosis over time. Projections were available in a 360-day calendar format, which made it necessary to remove a few days from the 365 days-per-year empirical data to compare the modelled observations to it. Annual population projections by regions up to 2043 were downloaded from NOMIS for England¹⁷,

¹⁵ RCP 8.5 refers to the atmospheric conditions that produce global warming at an average of 8.5 W/m² by 2100, (Riahi et al., 2011). See together with Chapter 2.2.2.

¹⁶ The data on this web site are available under the Open Government Licence, see: <http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/>

¹⁷ NOMIS is a service provided by Office for National Statistics (ONS): https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/datasets/ppsyoala/view?geography=2092957699&projected_year=2018,2019,2020,2021,2022,2023,2024,2025,2026,2027,2028,2029,2030,2031,2032,2033,2034,2035,2036,2037,2038,2039,2040,2041,2042,2043&geography=2092957699&gender=0,1,2&rows=projected_year,geography&cols=gender&tools=hidden

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5 and from StatsWales for Wales¹⁸ in a shapefile format. Projections beyond this year were not available due to the uncertainty associated with longer term demographic forecasting. QGIS Desktop 3.16.11 was used to spatially assign the demographic projections into a 60km grid to match the climate projections.

7.2.2 Application of the model in the data forecast

The conditional incidence calculated in England and Wales in Chapter 5 for maximum air temperature, precipitation and daylength was applied for all the 15 MetOffice Hadley members. The open source code is available at: <https://github.com/lauracris-7/Conditional-Incidence-Salmonella/tree/main/Climate-change-application>.

For instances where the associated cases recorded in situations with very low number of residents exposed to the same weather variables, the calculation throws a falsely increased incidence due to very low denominators. To navigate these misleading large predictions in small populations, I excluded the bottom 0.127% of the observations, which corresponded to catchment areas with less than 3,746 residents. Additionally, incidence values for unprecedented weather conditions for which there was no previous record in England and Wales were extrapolated from the conditional incidence based on day length and maximum air temperature. The incidence was estimated from a multiple linear regression based on a 3-degree polynomial term for both day length and maximum air temperature, which allowed to capture more complex, non-linear relationships between the variables. The number of novel weather instances for which incidence had to be extrapolated for all the years studied accounted for 9.38% of the weather projections (Figure 7-1). The most numerous novel weather conditions are expected for September and October, with record high temperatures. A similar pattern was observed in a breakdown for every year studied (Figure G-2).

¹⁸ Welsh Government's online repository for detailed statistical data for Wales: <https://statswales.gov.wales/Catalogue/Population-and-Migration/Population/Projections/Local-Authority/2018-based/populationprojections-by-localauthority-year>

Figure 7-1. Cumulative count of missing weather data instances per postcode on a daily basis. Each data point corresponds to the total number of instances where a novel climate condition was forecasted by all climate members and for every future year studied. An average of 1,500 instances were absent per member per year.

7.3 Reconstruction of modelled cases in a climate change scenario

The prediction of salmonellosis cases produced by the model according to each of the different members is somewhat variable (See Figure G-1 in the supplementary material for an example for the projections of each member for the year 2043). The individual salmonellosis cases predicted by the model for all 15 members were combined and evaluated together for a same year of study in order to account for the whole range of possible weather scenarios, which is reflected in the ribbon of the reconstruction plot (Figure 7-2).

The cases of salmonellosis predicted by the model for each year studied were broadly consistent, with isolated outliers in the form of spikes. By dividing the sum of the mean values of empirical cases by predicted cases by the model (bolded line, Figure 7-2), it can be concluded that an **overall increase of 17% of cases would be expected by 2043**, with a notable increase of cases in the first half of the year. And more particularly a drop or a plateau effect is observed in the modelled cases across all years in August-September, a time when the empirical data present the highest number of observed cases. This phenomenon does not seem to be explained by temperature, since temperature is projected to be continuously higher from June to November. However, the average precipitation during August and September are lower than the historical records. An increase in modelled cases is detectable from mid-May for all years, and a crest at the end of April in 2040. Both events coincide with decreased average rain projections. By 2043 a relatively, mild flattening effect is observed in

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5 cases, levelling out the historically marked peak of September with an increase in cases from January to April and from April to mid-June. These events coincide with an increase in predicted temperature and precipitation. A decline in cases in the month of July matching with decreased precipitations.

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5

Figure 7-2. Continued on next page.

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5

Figure 7-2. Continued on next page.

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5

Figure 7-2. Continued on next page.

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5

Figure 7-2. Continued on next page.

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5

Figure 7-2. For legend see next page.

Burden of human salmonellosis expected under a scenario of climate change RCP 8.5

According to the findings of Chapter 5, an increase in salmonellosis cases would be expected in drier and warmer conditions at the beginning of the year (upper left figure), as well as for dry and warm conditions for February to March and November to December (9-12h of day length, Figure 5-4 upper right). The highest risk period would be found for April-May and Sept-Oct (12-15 h/day, Figure 5-4 lower left), where higher risk of infection is associated with higher amounts precipitations pose for temperatures up to 15°C, and to dry conditions when greater than 15°C. For the longest and hottest days of the year, the risk is higher for intermediate precipitation levels (1-3 mm/day) (Figure 5-4 lower right) with an interesting decreased risk in the absence of precipitations.

7.4 Discussion

The UKCP18 forecasts project a progressive rise in temperatures as well as wetter winters and drier summers, with a particular impact in southern England (Bernie et al., 2018). Should the impact of temperature on the incidence of salmonellosis be linear, a notable increase in summer cases would be expected in the coming years. However, the presented model does not forecast this pattern when taking into account the effect of precipitation and day length in addition to temperature. Rather, new seasonal peaks of incidence could be expected in May and July. This highlights the importance of accounting for the complex effect of interacting weather factors on the incidence of salmonellosis.

Some limitations of the model include sample and observation bias among others, as described in Chapter 6. Public health interventions and individual human behaviour (medical seeking, case notification, eating habits, etc.) are unavoidably linked to incidence data and this cannot be detached from the data with certainty. The methodology assumes the absence of major changes in public health interventions or behavioural changes in the years studied

*Figure 7-2. Reconstruction of daily salmonellosis cases predicted in England and Wales by the model according to the 15 MetOffice Hadley Centre climate members (HadGEM3-GC3.05) for a RCP 8.5 scenario. **Upper:** comparison of average empirical detrended cases for 1999-2016 (red) with predicted cases by the model for a 5-year study interval from 2025 to 2043 (turquoise). The solid lines represent the mean number. The shaded ribbons represent the 25% and 75% quantiles of the model for all members (light turquoise); and the 25% and 75% of the averaged empirical cases for all year-case records (light red). The scale of reconstructed cases was intentionally fixed at 40 for graphical convenience, despite uncertainty of the model having higher values not shown. **Lower:** in colour, mean precipitation and maximum air temperature projections. In grey, historical precipitation and temperature records for 1999-2016 for comparative purposes. The shaded ribbons are the 25th and 75th percentile of the data, informing on the variability on weather projections for all members (coloured) and interannual weather variation for the years 1999-2016 (grey).*

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compared to the current situation in England and Wales. This assumption is based on the burden of salmonellosis and the observed incidence patterns from 2000 to 2016. It is worth noting that the epidemiological situation and the surveillance system in place during the years used to feed the model could be a source of bias for future epidemiological scenarios.

In addition to the uncertainty associated to the nature of the climate projections²⁰, a limitation of the statistical model lies in its limited predictive power under novel weather conditions not previously recorded. In the current analysis, 9.4% of weather conditions forecasted for 2025-2043 were never observed in England and Wales. These values were extrapolated from the nearest experienced values. However, given its novelty, the performance of these extrapolations should be interpreted with caution. To date, this is the first study that analyses the interconnected effect of weather factors on the risk of salmonellosis in the context of climate change. This information can prove useful to health professionals and Public Health officers to be more alert to the potential increase in cases at unusual times of the year. Promptly recognition of these patterns could reduce the consequent opportunity costs derived from sickness absences and plan for early detection, preventive measures and resource allocation.

²⁰ For more information on caveats and limitations, see:

<https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/research/approach/collaboration/ukcp/data/caveats>

Chapter 8

Temperature, food sources and risk of salmonellosis: a mechanistic approach

8.1 Context

As mentioned in Chapter 2.1.4, food is the main source of *Salmonella* infection in humans, with eggs and chicken being among the most common food sources of infection. In Chapter 2.2.1, temperature was highlighted as a relevant factor that promotes bacterial multiplication, rightly directing numerous investigations towards assessing its impact on salmonella infection. This is in line with the findings from the conditional incidence model of Chapter 5, where temperature was found to have an outstanding influence in most processes involved in human infection caused by the consumption of food contaminated with *Salmonella* (Figure 8-1, processes 1 and 3).

The question that arises now is whether a simplified analysis of the main weather factors and sources of salmonellosis would suffice to predict salmonellosis incidence. This chapter aims to determine whether the **effect of temperature** on bacterial multiplication **in the main food sources** linked to salmonellosis infections could explain the observed seasonal pattern of salmonellosis incidence. I will combine mathematical modelling and bacterial kinetic responses in food to model *Salmonella* growth under the effect of daily mean air temperature. For this, I will explore the mechanisms involved in infection as a chain of events, namely the rate of *Salmonella* growth in chicken and eggs leading to disease while considering the estimated amount of food consumed by a susceptible individual. Finally, I will compare the results with the findings from the conditional incidence model to assess whether the bacterial growth in chicken and eggs as a function of temperature is sufficient to estimate and explain the risk of salmonellosis.

Figure 8-1. Main sources of *Salmonella* infection originating in contaminated animal faeces: (1) cross-contamination of food for human consumption, (2) direct infection, and (3) contamination of irrigation water and soil used for fruit and vegetable crops, including the use of animal manure as fertilizer. Image created using BioRender.

8.2 Description of the model

Residents in the catchment area were assumed to have the same probability of consuming food (e.g., one egg and one portion of raw chicken) exposed to the local air temperature and with a low initial contamination of 10 CFU for simplicity purposes. Doses above 10^2 CFU have a probability of causing illness ranging from 0.5 to 1.0, and doses less than 10^2 CFU have probability of illness ranging from 0.01 to 0.56 (Teunis et al., 2010). Nonetheless, the infectious dose will depend on the food vehicle in consideration as well as other factors external (e.g., the climate conditions, the time passed from contamination to consumption of the source, storage conditions and handling and cooking practices). The number of residents per catchment area was used to estimate the proportion of cases due to chicken and egg assuming the equal consumption of a food product per person per day. I considered proportion and not absolute numbers because i) I was interested in seasonal variation and ii) lack of information on food consumption and prevalence of salmonella in food. The cases estimated were normalized by dividing its value by the sum of the total values in order to be comparable with empirical reported cases. The open-source code is available at: [https://github.com/lauracris-7/Conditional Incidence Salmonella/tree/main/Climate change application](https://github.com/lauracris-7/Conditional-Incidence-Salmonella/tree/main/Climate-change-application).

The modified Ratkowsky equation (see Equation 3-4, page 38) derived from the Baranyi model (Baranyi & Roberts, 1994) was used to calculate the maximum growth rate for *S. Enteritidis* by fitting observed growth data in egg yolk (at $7 \leq T \leq 45^\circ\text{C}$) (Equation 8-1) (Gumudavelli et al., 2007) and chicken meat (at $10 \leq T \leq 45^\circ\text{C}$) (Equation 8-2) (Juneja et al., 2007). The Baranyi

Temperature, food sources and risk of salmonellosis: a mechanistic approach model is comparable to the Gompertz equation and is commonly used to describe bacterial growth data (Burnham et al., 2006; Gumudavelli et al., 2007; Juneja et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020; Santillana Farakos et al., 2013; Velugoti et al., 2011). Here, I used Baranyi's model as it is the one I found in the literature describing growth data in both food sources (Figure 8-2).

$$\mu_{max}(\text{egg}) = 0.002065 (T - 6.13)^2 (1 - \exp [0.27469(T - 46.26)]), \quad \text{Equation 8-1}$$

$$\mu_{max}(\text{chicken}) = 0.0019 (T - 3.35)^2 (1 - \exp [0.29(T - 48.01)]), \quad \text{Equation 8-2}$$

where μ_{max} is the maximum specific growth rate in $\log_e\text{CFU/g}$ in 1/h. The effect of temperature on *Salmonella* growth kinetics available in the literature in eggs and raw chicken portrays the sigmoidal pattern typical of the Gompertz curve (see Chapter 3.2.1). An exponential growth phase starting at 10°C reaches its peak at temperatures around 40°C (Figure 8-2).

Figure 8-2. Growth curves as a function of temperature of *S. Enteritidis* in egg yolk (turquoise) (Gumudavelli et al., 2007), and *Salmonella* ssp. in chicken meat (red) (Juneja et al., 2007) produced with a Baranyi model.

In order to assess the relevance of temperature in causing salmonellosis through chicken and eggs, the resulting cases estimated from the maximum bacterial load in chicken and eggs (mechanistic approach) are compared with the conditional incidence calculated for mean temperature (statistical approach), (Figure 8-5 and Supplementary Figure E-7).

Maximum bacterial load was assumed to be proportional to maximum bacterial growth under the assumptions that all food sources are subjected, on average, to the same growing times (*e.g.*, on average eggs were left outside the refrigerator for 5 hours). The incidence of salmonellosis conditional to temperature was estimated considering all locations and days when the temperature is T_0 , and assuming that food is exposed to this temperature for sufficient time as described above. The conditional incidence is explained by accounting for the number of cases: $\sum(N_{residents}(T_0) * \chi^{source}(T_0))$, and the total number of exposed people: $\sum(N_{residents}(T_0))$. The resulting conditional incidence is: $\chi^{source} = \alpha * \mu_{max}$, where α is an unknown constant of proportionality. The exact constant of proportionality was not considered important in this chapter, as the emphasis was placed on the proportion over the absolute number of cases, as mentioned above.

8.3 Results

The normalized cases of human salmonellosis estimated by the mechanistic model from bacterial growth in chicken meat and eggs (*i.e.*, the product of μ_{max} times the number of residents, summed across all catchments areas) broadly capture the seasonal incidence of cases reported to UKHSA (Figure 8-3). Cases due to both chicken and egg display very similar patterns to the reported cases, which match the yearly temperature oscillations, including the lowest reporting peak at the end of the year. When collapsing reported and modelled cases due to both chicken and eggs for all years, both curves reach their peak at approximately the same time, showcasing synchronization in their temporal patterns. Remarkably, both exhibit a distinctive double-peak phenomenon. However, the modelled curve exhibits a steeper slope that contrast with the smoother profile of the reported curve. (Figure 8-4).

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Figure 8-3. **Top:** Simulation of normalized cases of salmonellosis from chicken (green) and eggs (blue) in function of temperature, and recorded salmonellosis infections from UKHSA, former PHE (red) for the years 2000-2016 in England and Wales. Minimum and maximum temperature records showed in grey. Both the simulation and the historic records follow a clear pattern following rising temperatures. **Bottom:** sample of years 2010-2016 for small detail appreciation.

Figure 8-4. Overlap of the total weekly salmonellosis cases for the years 2000-2016 for a more visual reproduction of the seasonal pattern of the predicted cases (blue) against the UKHSA reported cases (red).

Given that the growth of *Salmonella* in chicken and eggs did not include consumption data, the shape of the curves of mechanistic and statistical approaches is evaluated for a comparison in performance instead of the absolute values (Figure 8-5). The slopes of the estimated cases based on chicken and eggs are similar to the estimates based on temperature from the statistical approach, especially for temperatures above 5°C. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the slopes do not appear to be identical, and the modelled conditional incidence clearly does not capture the observed conditional incidence for low temperature.

Figure 8-5. Comparative of predicted cases from mechanistic (red in chicken, turquoise in eggs) and conditional incidence approach (black). Values have been normalised by dividing the values by the total in order to be comparable.

8.4 Discussion

According to a European project on consumers behaviour, 40% of the salmonellosis cases registered in 2018 in six European countries took place in the household environment (Møretrø et al., 2021). In the same study, it was suggested that eggs from free-range hens may carry more contamination on their surface. On the other hand, production of free range retail eggs has more than doubled between 2006 and 2016 in the UK (Defra, 2017). This type of egg production is more susceptible to weather variations and *Salmonella* contamination (Parisi et al., 2015). The production system could be a potential contributing factor that hinder a complete disinfection of laying farms, perpetuating salmonellosis infections associated to eggs. In regard to chicken meat production, further research is needed to confirm the impact of the production system on bacterial contamination. However, there is some evidence showing that small retailers and meat shops could be linked with higher contamination levels (Public Health England, 2019). Consumption and production trends could play a determinant role on the level of exposure to weather conditions, which varies across locations.

The mechanistic approach used in this chapter assessed the interconnection between temperature and salmonellosis incidence from the main food sources involved in infection, leading to incidence predictions assuming a uniform contamination of food and constant eating patterns across the country. This similarity between reported and modelled cases in

Temperature, food sources and risk of salmonellosis: a mechanistic approach

the time series suggests that the effect of **temperature** in chicken meat and eggs is a relevant contributor to the reported cases of salmonellosis. However, the mechanistic model did not capture the seasonality of disease events as accurately as the conditional incidence approach. The disparity of the curves revealed by superimposing all the years of study suggests that modelling bacterial growth in eggs and chicken products is not sufficient to accurately reproduce seasonal patterns of salmonellosis cases. Other food products (*e.g.*, vegetables, ready to eat food) and other weather-driven mechanisms are likely to contribute to the observed incidence. In order to further improve the incidence estimations due to ingestion of a contaminated product, other factors could be included in the model, such as average bacteria ingested per serving (contamination dose), minimum hazardous dose allowing to calculate the likelihood of salmonella case in different susceptible groups, serving size, rate of consumption in the country/average consumption per capita per day, cooking conditions, and socio-economic factors (age, ethnicity, urban/rural), which have been proved to have a contribution to disease elsewhere (Rajan et al., 2017). Sales data of chicken and eggs from a prominent supermarket chain was explored for this chapter but was ultimately rejected due to its financial costs. Nonetheless, the main objective of this analysis was to improve the understanding of the mechanisms leading to salmonellosis disease.

The contribution of weather factors other than temperature as well as sources of reporting delay to adjust from bacterial multiplication to case-reporting were explored in Chapter 5. The incidence conditional to temperature alone captures similar patterns of the observed incidence from both mechanistic and statistical approaches (*i.e.*, a turning point around 5°C, followed by a constant increase). However, some quantitative discrepancies in the slope of the conditional incidence can be observed at temperature above 5°C and qualitative discrepancies at low temperatures. As no consumption data was available, I focused only on qualitative shape of the curves and not on the number of predictions. This suggests that, even if temperature is an important driver of disease, there are other factors that need to be included to improve salmonellosis predictions and foodborne transmission alone is not sufficient to explain the patterns of salmonellosis observed in England and Wales.

Chapter 9

Final discussion

9.1 Summary of findings

The association between disease and weather has been consolidated with the advances in weather forecast and the availability of high-resolution predictions, motivating the development of predictive models. Such models are designed to provide early warning of impending epidemics which, if accurate, would be invaluable for epidemic preparedness and prevention (Rogers et al., 2010). Statistical models are useful tools for providing insight of disease dynamics and their associated risk factors to motivate preventive actions. Traditional time series regression models (*e.g.*, auto-regressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models) are commonly used for practical forecasting of diseases to accommodate possible preventive interventions at the public health level (Lal et al., 2013; Rojas & Ibacache-Quiroga, 2020). Their predictive power lies in accounting for past cases as proxies for future events, which is effective for short-term incidence predictions, especially in the case of highly transmissible diseases like flu. However, these models do not go further in assessing the effect of the interacting factors behind disease events.

The complexity and multifactorial mechanisms involved in the occurrence of infectious diseases make any prediction challenging. Despite this, the striking association between weather and seasonal incidence pattern of certain diseases, such as salmonellosis, was the motivation for this thesis to study the main factors involved in seasonality of salmonellosis and to estimate reported cases to health authorities based on weather forecast. Aware of the important role of environment in salmonellosis, other authors have investigated the effect of one weather variable at a time on salmonellosis, focusing usually on the weather variables with a well-known linkage to disease, such as temperature, rainfall, and, to a less extent, relative humidity (Bashir et al., 2022; Kovats et al., 2004; Milazzo et al., 2016b).

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Despite the control strategies implemented by different countries to reduce the burden of salmonellosis, including improved biosecurity and vaccination policies, *Salmonella* continues to be a relevant cause of gastrointestinal disease. Improper animal and food handling, as well as environmental contamination and persistence, are considered to be the main reasons for the difficulty in eradicating this persistent infection (Oastler et al., 2019). In the UK, the number of community cases is estimated to be 3.2 (95% CI: 1.4-12.0) times more than what is reported to national authorities (Wheeler et al., 1999) and as high as 14 (5-95% quartiles: 3.6-56) for the Netherlands (Kemmeren et al., 2006).

The methodology used in this thesis builds on the conditional incidence model developed by (Lo Iacono et al., 2024), which studied the effect of weather on the incidence of campylobacteriosis. By adapting the model to *Salmonella*, I improved our understanding of the disease dynamics at the weather-disease interface and demonstrated the ability to estimate patterns of salmonellosis incidence based on information of weather factors. The novelty of this methodology lies in the exploration of multiple (14) meteorological factors and their three-way interaction at a high spatial resolution. The approach exploited the linkage of about 145,000 salmonellosis cases over 17 years in England and Wales with meteorological datasets at the same resolution scale, without relying on assumptions or regression analysis. In contrast to aggregated data, the use of salmonellosis notifications at daily resolution allowed to identify with high precision the effect of weather on infections on the likely day of infection.

The model satisfactorily reproduced empirical incidence patterns of human salmonellosis and, more importantly, identified and characterized the most and least relevant weather factor combinations associated with salmonellosis. In effect, temperature amplitude, sunshine duration and air pressure were found to not perform well when reproducing empirical cases, while windspeed had a variable effect depending on the factors with which it is in combination. Water-based factors explored (*i.e.*, relative humidity and precipitation) seemed to have a lower impact as compared to temperature (mean, maximum, and dewpoint temperature). In addition to temperature, moisture level, measured as water activity, is another relevant measurement of bacterial stability in food. The water activity is specific to every food product, and varies depending on the preparation (*e.g.*, marination), freshness

level (water content), packaging technology, etc. Given the atmospheres controls in the food industry, it is arguable to attribute outdoor conditions a decisive role on the bacterial growth on the food. Perhaps shelf life and storage conditions have a greater impact on the water activity of a food product than the meteorological conditions (Sandulachi, 2012). Therefore, even if environmental weather were to have an impact in the water activity of food, it is likely to be very small due to the packaging and preservation techniques applied to the marketed food products.

The suitability of the different weather factor combinations for estimating the risk of salmonellosis was assessed visually. Nevertheless, a straightforward approach to assess the performance of the model numerically could involve a simple sum of the squares of the differences between the mean of the cases reported across all the locations and the expected modelled cases. However, relying solely in this method may draw misleading conclusions. For instance, a model capable of reproducing the seasonal pattern of reported cases, but which consistently underreports the historical data, could be wrongly considered less accurate than a model that does not effectively capture the curve despite producing a sum of mean values similar to the observed data. Plotting of residuals, typically used for residual diagnostics employed in regression models (Feng et al., 2020), could give a better indication of the discrepancies between the model and empirical data. For example, to explore whether the residuals are symmetrical around zero, the presence of outliers, or detecting potential trends. Analysis of the confusion matrix is another potential metric to assess the Sensitivity of the model (*i.e.*, the percentage of individuals the model correctly predicted as a case of salmonellosis), the Specificity (the percentage of individuals the model correctly predicted not be a salmonellosis case) and thus the total misclassification rate (*i.e.*, the percentage of total incorrect classifications). Analysis of the Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) graphs could also identify the optimal values of some of the continuous parameters used here (*e.g.*, the time-lag) that result in the best compromise in terms of sensitivity and specificity (Fawcett, 2006; Sykes et al., 2022).

A partial correlation coefficient approach, briefly mentioned in Chapter 5, could be further explored to identify the most relevant weather factors, as well as to test conditional independence. This technique allows to explore the specific relationship between two

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variables while controlling for the possible confounding effect of a third variable. For example, we can observe the modelled incidence resulting from increasing temperature, humidity or day length by one unit and compare them to discern which weather factor influences the model results the most, and therefore, has a bigger influence on salmonellosis. This approach would further assist in identifying the most relevant weather factors to inform control strategies.

Some of the weather combinations found to excel in reproducing historical salmonellosis cases were mean, maximum and dewpoint temperature, mean and cumulative precipitation, relative humidity, and day length. In fact, an increase of 15.5% in salmonellosis incidence per degree centigrade was found for mean daily temperatures greater than 10°C in the months of April to June and July to October (12-15 hours long). The fact that the analysis of day length and temperature alone provides different results as compared to their combined effect (Supplementary Figures F-7 to F-9) reflects the complexity of how these factors are associated with the disease. The combination of three meteorological factors was selected with the aim to incorporate possible interconnections between factors that are unknown or non-obvious. Even if some of the factors may appear less important, their contribution in a three-way combination yields favorable outcomes as shown in previous work on campylobacteriosis (Lo Iacono et al., 2024). Therefore, in line with the precautionary principle, all three factors were included instead of just two. While it would be possible to include more than three factors in the model, their interpretation would become challenging. In addition, large data fluctuations due to reduced number of data points for each stratified subset would render the statistical analysis difficult. Three factors were deemed sufficient to capture interactions without complicating result interpretation.

Nonetheless, a sensitivity analysis is required to evaluate the impact of uncertainties around some of the chosen numerical inputs, and how they may affect the results. Numerical inputs that are subject to a different choice of their values include: the size of the bins used to stratify the weather factors as well as the order of the stratification, the spatial and temporal units used in the analysis (*e.g.*, one week rather than one day, and catchment area versus a squared grid), and the appropriateness of linking the weather to the location of the diagnostic laboratories as opposed to domestic or work address. The results from any of the numerical

validations of the model mentioned above, such as the confusion matrix, would give an indication of the sensitivity of the methodology to the nature of the inputs. From the findings of the conditional incidence analysis, one of the suitable weather factors combination was applied in the Netherlands, a country with a similar temperate climate, yielding to satisfactory results. The fact that the model built from epidemiological data from in England and Wales is applicable to the Netherlands suggests that the effect of weather on salmonellosis incidence is not limited to a specific geographical location but rather has a generalised effect. However, this conclusion would be strengthened should the model be applied to a country with social and climatic conditions that are most opposite to the UK, such as a country from a different continent and hemisphere.

Based on the demonstrated relevance of temperature and on the forecasted rise in temperatures in the coming years, a proportional increase in salmonellosis cases would be expected due to climate change. In fact, almost 20,000 annual cases are expected by 2040 linked only to temperature change; and up to a 50% increase based on population change alone by 2100 (Watkiss & Hunt, 2012). Assuming constant reporting patterns and the absence of relevant control measures, the conditional incidence model, based not only on future projections of temperature, but also precipitation, and in combination with day-length, predicted an overall increase of 17% in cases throughout the year 2043 and a potential new peak of cases in the end of May and in July. In 2019, the salmonellosis incidence reports in the UK started to display a compatible rising peak in May (UKHSA, 2021). If these findings are confirmed, salmonellosis could imply an additional burden on healthcare services, particularly when there is a simultaneous occurrence of cases from other diseases.

Given the relevance of temperature as modulator of salmonellosis identified by the model, it is reasonable to think that temperature is the main weather factor acting over the most common food sources of salmonellosis outbreaks would be good estimators of future disease. I therefore explored a mechanistic approach which assumes that infections are originating from bacterial growth in food, which in turn would be the underlying cause for the observed patterns of incidence. The approach captured the general seasonal patterns of the disease, albeit with some discrepancies that prevented drawing clear conclusions. The shape of the curve arising from the theoretical conditional model partially resembled the shape of the

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empirical model (*i.e.*, both increasing after a certain value of temperature but with different rates). Overall, this suggests that, although temperature and microbial growth in chicken and eggs may play a major role in salmonellosis incidence (Wheeler et al., 1999), other explanatory factors that may have an additional role in inducing disease should be investigated. At the same time, the inclusion of other food sources of contamination weighted with their consumption rates would improve the predictions of salmonellosis due to food poisoning. This would be a big challenge given that most food sources of salmonellosis infection are unknown or mixed sources (EFSA and ECDC, 2022).

9.2 Conclusions

This thesis contributes to broadening our understanding of the disease dynamics at the weather-disease interface and demonstrated the ability to predict incidence based on historical experience. A good understanding of the relationship between cases recorded and relevant regulating factors is needed in order to anticipate the magnitude and timing of peak incidence and to predict demand on health care resources. Despite the conditional incidence model alone was not enough to provide a comprehensive mechanistic understanding of the salmonellosis incidence, it can provide relevant insights.

The conditional incidence is a simple yet effective methodology for analysing the seasonality of salmonellosis with the advantage to be easily performed and adapted to different countries, when long-term and high geographic resolution surveillance data are available. In England and Wales, it pointed to the combined effect of mean temperature, precipitation and day length as suggested combination for analysing the burden of salmonellosis. However, other combinations also lead to satisfactory predictions. Despite the reporting bias linked to the nature of the incidence data analysed, the model works well in reproducing the reporting patterns of human salmonellosis and, more importantly, in identifying and narrowing down the most relevant weather parameters with an effect on *Salmonella*, allowing to estimate the influence in present and future climate scenarios. This study offers valuable insight into the underlying mechanisms of seasonality involved in the final number of reported cases, such as population behaviour and environmental effects on host and pathogen to be further

explored. This knowledge is essential for disease preparedness and prevention, especially concerning the increasing anthropogenic impact on the environment and climate change.

Unavoidably, the conditional incidence methodology has some limitations. Due to the numerous factors involved in the seasonality of diseases, such as a time lag between a meteorological event and its impact on incidence, human behaviours towards food hygiene, the particularities of climate and topography of a location, etc., the methodology is unable to fully isolate the role of weather. This is noted in the minor disagreement between simulated and reported cases for England and Wales in the reconstruction graphs. At the same time, the human behaviour component inherent to the nature of the surveillance data (*e.g.*, reporting patterns and health-seeking behaviour of the patients) as well as location-specific particularities of salmonellosis infections (*e.g.*, different serotype predominance, which may have a different response to weather, distribution of susceptible population, etc.) make it necessary to adapt the model prior to its application to a different country. This need for adaptation becomes evident in the application of the model in the Netherlands. Finally, the model is based on historical evidence, which implies a reduced performance in novel situations, such as unexperienced conditions of climate change.

When modelling, a series of assumptions need to be taken in order to shed light in some parts of the whole that is known. The conditional incidence model cannot answer why certain factor combinations work better than others, why day length forms better than radiation; is day length involved in the causal pathway or is just a proxy for time of the year, how to distinguish causation from correlation. The answers are only speculative at this point, but that does not undervalue the practical utility of the study. With data-based evidence, insightful conclusions were drawn, allowing for timely and targeted contention action.

The social component influencing the occurrence of salmonellosis is evident in the uneven and abrupt distribution of cases. Should weather be the only driver of disease, a gradual dispersal of cases would be expected as weather variables generally vary gradually. Human behaviour is assumed to play a determining role in salmonellosis incidence and partly be the responsible of the seasonality pattern observed in humans. A good example of this is reflected in the number of laboratory notifications dropping by 69% in the EU (EFSA and ECDC, 2021b).

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The observed change in reporting trends is most likely related to the COVID-19 pandemic, and more specifically to the decrease in eating out habits and attendance at large events. Human activity is one of the components harder to model, both due to the arbitrary nature and its heterogeneity. In fact, the effect of case reporting is a non-negligible conditioning factor of subsequent cases (Pritchard et al., 2022). Perceived risk may influence not only more protective behaviours on consumers, but also higher rate of diagnosis and reporting in local health facilities, which may turn in biased and non-comparable reported cases. This effect, however, is not dismissed, but is assumed inherent to the data used.

The conditional incidence is a transparent methodology for finding striking associations between factors that may not be obvious at first sight. A great applicability of the model would be its integration with weather forecasts so that warning messages could be disseminated for risky weather conditions. Should international health agencies such as EFSA would be interested in coordinating a data collection across all European countries, the model would be strengthened and the integration of surveillance and awareness strategies could be more effective.

9.3 Recommendations for future work

The methodology does not identify the causal pathway of the disease, albeit the robust association with the weather factors might generate insights of the mechanism. Following the favourable comparison of the modelled time series with empirical data, the analysis was limited to combinations of based on the available data, but other weather or environmental factors not accounted for in this study might play a role in driving the disease. Proximity to animal farms (Behravesch et al., 2014; Lal et al., 2012), presence of garden birds as bacterial reservoir (B. Lawson et al., 2014), human behaviour (Wang et al., 2018), or land use (Arnold et al., 2021) are example of data that could be included in future research. For instance, by estimating incidence of salmonellosis conditional to the average number of livestock present in the catchment area. Human behaviour could be further investigated by analysing the halves of the year with the same day duration to shed light in determining whether the time of the year is an additional explanatory variable, possibly related to different human activity for different time of the year. At the same time, the analysis of more than three simultaneous

weather variables is possible with this model, if considered relevant. The current model only skimmed over the effect of time-lag, which was done on the basis of trial and error. A more systematic approach is needed to objectively assess the effect of time-lag on the disease, including variable time lags for different weather factors.

Although the contribution of the conditional incidence to the existing knowledge on *Salmonella* remains phenomenological and does not elaborate on the reasons involved on the observed associations of weather and incidence, it contributes substantially to formulating theories on the underlying mechanism. Further research would involve exploring additional mechanisms involved in the impact of the relevant weather factors identified in this thesis (e.g., mean air temperature, dewpoint temperature, relative humidity or day length), aiming to quantify their effects on disease progression. The conditional incidence could be applied in conjunction with in-depth experimental and social research to infer robust mechanistic theories. For example, to test the hypothesis of salmonellosis infection driven by outdoor barbecues on a warm day, extensive retail chicken sales data could be added as a variable. These theories could be then used to feed a theoretical agent-based model (that would mimic the mechanism of interest to be tested) and compared with the conditional incidence for acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis. At the same time, the model can be adapted to other locations as well as other infectious agents with no human-to-human transmission. However, any additional adaptation of the code is currently very time consuming, which calls for a model rendering and automation. Also, it would be interesting to compare this with predictions from machine learning. Finally, the amount of incidence and weather data that shape the conditional incidence could be increased with other countries' historical data, leading to stronger and more accurate predictions.

9.4 Concluding remarks

Biology is a complex and inexact science. Estimating the occurrence of foodborne disease is daunting and long-time explored. Unavoidably, high number of assumptions needed to be done in order to convey a message regarding risk and disease prevention, putting in evidence the numerous gaps in our understanding of salmonellosis. As well stated by Hedberg, “the real challenge is to identify the gaps in our knowledge so that they can be systematically addressed and updated estimates of foodborne illness can be provided to guide prevention efforts and assess the effectiveness of current food safety measures (CDC, 1999) “.

Environment is the cornerstone of disease. The environment is the vehicle that enables an infectious agent to get in contact with a susceptible host for a disease event to occur. Preparedness and prevention may sound distant in the absence of an immediate threat. However, this does not make it any less important or timely to be ready for the worst-case scenario. Numerous threats and potential causative agents for epidemics are all around, standing merely a small mutation away from becoming more lethal or breaching the species barrier to find a pool of susceptible hosts.

Weather, an important environmental driver. The conditional incidence model and its applicability to different location is a compelling evidence of the relevant and universal influencing effect of weather on salmonellosis. However, due to the multitude of transmission routes and weather scenarios, comprehensive research is necessary to unravel each involved mechanism. This thesis contributes to the growing body of knowledge by opening up several avenues for future research. The exploration of weather's influence on Salmonella provides insights that can be applied to other diseases and regions.

Application of this thesis to anticipate future burden of salmonellosis. Climate change is altering the frequency, severity, duration, and location of weather and climate phenomena. This includes rising temperatures, heavier rainfall and droughts, and some other forms of severe weather. These changes are already having an impacting on the frequency and severity of zoonotic diseases. Contributing as best as we can to anticipate their effects, even in a limited way, is a step towards being prepared for future pandemics.

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Appendix

A. Epidemiological reporting patterns in different periods of years

The effect of weather on the incidence of salmonellosis is expected to be constant over time. To verify that this is the case, the outcomes of the conditional incidence model for different periods of years were compared.

The combined effect of maximum air temperature, daylength and mean precipitation were explored at three different periods of years (1) 1989-1993, (2) 2000-2005, and (3) 2012-2016. The year ranges were selected based on observable differences in incidence patterns (*i.e.*, higher incidence of the 90's, intermediate after the implementation of vaccination strategy in eggs, and latest years with lower incidence). The conditional incidence curves are expected to exhibit a similar shape for different time periods, albeit a variation in magnitude based on the number of cases reported in each time interval. This difference in magnitude is expected to be removed when using a detrended time series. However, I observed marginally different patterns in the conditional incidence (day length 11-14 and 14-16) between the pre-vaccination time (interval 1 from 1989-1993) and the latter periods (Figure A-1). I interpreted the effect of weather on observed incidence as potentially changing due to a shift in reporting patterns over time. Given the difference in incidence figures before and after the implementation of control strategies, notably vaccination, the years 2000-2016 were chosen for analysis.

Interval 1: 1989-1993

Interval 2: 2000-2005

Interval 3: 2012-2016

Figure A-1. Daily conditional incidence performed over different time periods for exploring a potential change of salmonellosis reporting response to weather. Note the increasing uncertainty as less data is included in the analysis (i.e., less number of cases in the last interval explored).

B. Smoothing techniques considered

Three smoothing techniques were explored to correct for non-uniform reporting rate: simple moving average, triangular moving average and kernel smoothing (kernel density estimation). Smoothing temporal data often reveals longer-term trends or cycles while smoothing over noise and short-term fluctuations. Our objective was to reduce the weekend and holiday (including half-term holidays) reporting bias while maintaining the seasonal pattern.

The performance of all smoothing methods tested did not identify a clear dominant method by visual inspection. Following the “Occam’s approach”, and given the similar smoothing effect of all techniques, the commonly used simple moving average was chosen. A time window multiple of 7 is desired, so that cases are consistently averaged within a calendar week (Monday to Sunday), avoiding possible bias due to repetition of the same weekday in successive moving averages. A 7 and 14-days interval were considered for correcting the reporting gaps (Figure B-1). By averaging over 14 days, the smoothing effect included 7 days prior and post “holiday” season, considering an average holiday duration of 7 days. However, 7-day interval was considered a good compromise between correcting for reporting bias while preserving a closer linkage between weather conditions and case reporting.

Figure B-1: Comparative of SMA smoother technique over 0, 7 and 14 days for years 1989-1996 for illustrative purposes. A clear weekly gap is seen when no smoothing technique is applied (left). Smoothing with a 7 and a 14-day window (middle and right, respectively) visually improves the reporting gaps without losing the seasonal pattern. However, consistent troughs of cases reported remained evident around end of April-beginning of May, and at the end of July-beginning of August. These declines are compatible with school holiday periods (Easter, summer and Christmas).

C. Descriptive statistics on weather factors

	mean	sd	median	trimmed	mad	min	max	range	skew	kurtosis	se
Sum daily salmonellosis cases	22.04	14.47	18	19.72	10.38	1	104	103	1.62	2.87	0.18
Global radiation	11247.1	6077.64	12010.94	11182.24	7316.42	734.34	30728.64	29994.3	-0.01	-1.08	17.71
Maximum air temperature	13.68	4.91	14.74	13.94	5.1	-2.38	27.87	30.25	-0.45	-0.6	0.01
Mean air temperature	11.88	4.63	12.96	12.16	4.79	-4.3	23.21	27.51	-0.49	-0.61	0.01
Minimum ai temperature	9.97	4.44	10.94	10.23	4.65	-6.43	20.77	27.21	-0.48	-0.61	0.01
Mean cloud cover	5.53	0.85	5.63	5.59	0.79	1.47	7.76	6.29	-0.72	0.68	0
Mean dewpoint temperature	8.62	4.11	9.6	8.89	4.21	-5.69	17.87	23.56	-0.54	-0.54	0.01
Mean surface air pressure	1004.97	7.99	1005.46	1005.26	7.02	954.43	1035.03	80.6	-0.51	1.72	0.03
Cumulative Precipitation	15.9	12.04	13.38	14.57	11.78	0.02	87.81	87.8	0.97	0.67	0.04
Mean Precipitation	2.27	1.72	1.91	2.08	1.68	0	12.54	12.54	0.97	0.67	0.01
Relative humidity	81.78	5.31	81.94	81.92	5.41	59.21	95.3	36.09	-0.25	-0.18	0.02
Sunshine duration	4.66	2.18	4.56	4.58	2.37	0.13	13.23	13.1	0.34	-0.31	0.01
Day length	12.98	2.94	13.42	13.13	3.72	7.16	17.38	10.22	-0.34	-1.18	0.01
Temperature amplitude	3.71	1.39	3.44	3.57	1.26	0.73	16.02	15.29	0.95	0.97	0
Temperature indoor	21	0.05	21	21	0	21	23.21	2.21	25.82	738.1	0
Relative humidity indoor	0.49	0.12	0.5	0.49	0.14	0.17	0.82	0.65	-0.16	-0.88	0

Table C-1. Overview of the weather values distribution for 1989-2016. sd: standard deviation from the mean (dispersion of data); trimmed:10% top and bottom removed (outliers); mad: median absolute deviation; range: difference between maximum and minimum values (spread of the data); skew: measure of the asymmetry. A positive skewness indicates that the tail of the distribution is longer on the positive side, while a negative skewness indicates that the tail is longer on the negative side. Kurtosis: deviation from normal distribution. Positive kurtosis indicates a more peaked distribution than normal, while negative kurtosis indicates a flatter distribution than normal. Se: standard error (variation of the sample measure from the true population value). A smaller se indicates a closer measure to the true population value.

Distribution of weather values 2000-2016

Figure C-1. Distribution of weather values recorded for 2000-2016 in England and Wales. From left to right: maximum air temperature, mean air temperature, relative humidity, mean precipitation, dewpoint temperature (degrees Celsius), day length (hours), mean surface air pressure (hPa), and global radiation (kJ/m²). Note the disproportionate values of air pressure and global radiation.

D. Diagnostic laboratory data rendering

The postcode location of the salmonellosis cases reported had to be spatially linked with the location of the diagnostic laboratories and the census data of residents within the corresponding catchment areas. The Cartesian coordinates for the 416 diagnostic laboratories for gastrointestinal diseases were provided by UKHSA/PHE collaborators, while the data on the census by catchment areas was leveraged from a previous work on *Campylobacter*. Out of the 349 post code locations of the reported salmonellosis cases, a total of 207 cases were considered for the analysis based on their spatial connection to the laboratory and residents information (Figure D-2).

Figure D-2. Postcode data information available from the different spatial source.

Due to the prolonged duration of the surveillance data used in the analysis, there were instances where diagnostic laboratories closed or relocated during this period. As a consequence, discrepancies arose in the recorded locations of some laboratories over the years. To maintain accuracy and consistency in the data, meticulous checks and reallocations were conducted to address these discrepancies. From the locations with reported cases, 30 postcodes had no spatial information associated. This included 19 locations overseas, Northern Ireland [BT126BA, BT160RH, BT412RL, BT471SB, BT521TP, BT635QQ, BT746AY, BT790AP, BT97AB, BT97JB, BT97JR], Channel Islands [GY46UU, JE13QS], Isle of Man [IM14QA], and 11 locations derived from a deprecated or relocated laboratory. The latter were manually assigned to an operational diagnostic laboratory by proximity on Google Maps® (Google, 2021), and in no case greater than 1 km to the original postcodes. See Table D-2Table C-1 for the detailed decision made per reporting postcode.

324 postcodes out of the 349 where salmonellosis cases were reported matched the resident census available, from which 207 were allocated by our collaborators of PHE to their designated catchment area.

PC of reported case	Observation	Action
BT126BA	N. Ireland	Removed
BT160RH	N. Ireland	Removed
BT412RL	N. Ireland	Removed
BT471SB	N. Ireland	Removed
BT521TP	N. Ireland	Removed
BT635QQ	N. Ireland	Removed
BT746AY	N. Ireland	Removed
BT790AP	N. Ireland	Removed
BT97AB	N. Ireland	Removed
BT97JB	N. Ireland	Removed
BT97JR	N. Ireland	Removed
CB233RE	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	CB38RE
CV22DX	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	CV14FH
GY46UU	Channel Islands	Removed
IM14QA	Isle of Man	Removed
JE13QS	Channel Islands	Removed
NULL		Removed
NW4	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	NW97DG
NW95EQ	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	NW95HT
PE296NT	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	PE188NT
PE39GZ	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	PE36DA
SE1 6LH	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	SE11HF
SN90QJ	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	SN36BB
SS143BY	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	SS165NL
ST46QG	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	ST47PX
WD63FG	Non existent in Lab PC. Reassigned by proximity	WD63AU
Z993CZ	Overseas	Removed
ZZ993CZ	Overseas	Removed
ZZ993HZ	Overseas	Removed
ZZ993WZ	Overseas	Removed

Table D-2. Decision table on removing and relocation of each of the 30 postcodes of cases reported without a direct connection to the diagnostic laboratory information from PHE/UKHSA.

Alternatives were explored to extend the number of salmonellosis postcode locations to include in the analysis. However, the LSOA 2011 used to calculate the residents per catchment area was not publicly available at the NOMIS website²¹. The 2001 LSOA were available, but I

²¹<https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/query/construct/components/stdListComponent.asp?menuopt=12&subcomp=100>

considered to be outdated for estimating residents numbers. Since a shapefile of the catchment areas was not available to update resident numbers, incidence data up to 2016 was used in the analysis, which corresponded with the latest census data on resident population. This resulted in 1,313,675 instances from the salmonellosis incidence data with no spatial linkage to weather data, narrowing from 3,657,329 to 2,343,840 of total cases included in the analysis.

The postcodes excluded due to lack of resident information were:

B24DY, B743UP, BD161TW, BH11RW, BL97TD, BR67RG, BR69JU, BS28HW, BS67JJ, BS81BP, CB20SR, CB61DN, CF103NW, CF42XX, CO33NB, CT13NG, CV225PX, DA12HF, DL61JG, DL93DF, DT11TS, DY116RJ E14NL, E33HT, EC1A7BE, EN27PR, EN28JL, EX68PE, GL103RF, GU13LX, GU214BY, GU290BL, HA13RX, HA80AD, HP160EN, HP225PS, HX12YT, HX30PW, IG45PZ, IG95HX, KT153NB, L392AZ, L59YJ, LL111EG, LS212LY, LS224DN, LS270BT, LS29NL, M108WR, M139WL, M168AJ, M246DD, M274HA, ME45NG, ME59PG, NE14LP, NE461QJ, NE639JJ, NP77RX, NR128HP, NW117HX, NW17BY, NW89LE, NW89NH, NW97DG, OX169AL, OX169SA, PE166QZ, PL13JY, PO122AA, PO63LY, PO95NP, RG16UZ, RH15RH, RH164EX, RH60BB, S102JF, SA148QS, SE11HF, SE184LW, SE39UD, SE58AZ, SK82PX, SL24EG, SL36NH, SL43SJ, SM39DW, SS11EF, SW128HW, SW155PN, SW195NX, SW50TU, SY13EH, TF16TF, TN174AX, TN24UL, TN377RD, TN48AT, TQ148AH, TR182PF, TS201XZ, TS211EB, TW153AA, TW59QA, TW62JA, W106DZ, W1G6AZ, W1M7AF, W1N1DE, W1N2DH, W1T4JF, WA141PE, WC1N3BG, WC1V7PP, WD63AU, WR51DD.

E. Reconstruction of all weather factors tested

Figure E-1. Reconstruction of averaged modelled (turquoise) and laboratory-confirmed adjusted reported cases (red) conditional to **maximum air temperature** combined with other weather factors, and averaged at daily resolution across England and Wales for the years 2000-2016. Modelled cases were calculated according to their conditioning to combination of maximum air temperature and:

1. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Day length,
 2. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Global radiation,
 3. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Mean surface air pressure,
 4. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Sunshine duration,
 5. Mean Precipitation - Day length,
 6. Mean Precipitation - Global radiation,
 7. Mean Precipitation - Mean surface air pressure,
 8. Mean Precipitation - Sunshine duration,
 9. Relative Humidity - Day length,
 10. Relative Humidity - Global radiation,
 11. Relative Humidity - Mean surface air pressure,
 12. Relative Humidity - Sunshine duration.
- Combinations No. 1, 5 and 9 were considered to have a satisfactory fitting.

Figure E-2. Reconstruction of averaged modelled (turquoise) and laboratory-confirmed reported cases (red) conditional to **mean air temperature** combined with other weather factors, averaged at daily resolution across England and Wales for the years 2000-2016. Modelled cases were calculated according to their conditioning to combination of mean air temperature and:

1. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Day length,
2. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Global radiation,
3. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Mean surface air pressure,
4. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Sunshine duration,
5. Mean Precipitation - Day length,
6. Mean Precipitation - Global radiation,
7. Mean Precipitation - Mean surface air pressure,
8. Mean Precipitation - Sunshine duration,
9. Relative Humidity - Day length,
10. Relative Humidity - Global radiation,
11. Relative Humidity - Mean surface air pressure,
12. Relative Humidity - Sunshine duration.

Combinations No. 1, 5 and 9 were considered to have a satisfactory fitting.

Figure E-3. Reconstruction of averaged modelled (turquoise) and laboratory-confirmed reported cases (red) conditional to **mean dewpoint temperature** combined with other weather factors, averaged at daily resolution across England and Wales for the years 2000-2016. Modelled cases conditioning to combination of mean dewpoint temperature and:

1. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days)-Day length, 2. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days)-Global radiation, 3. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days)-Mean surface air pressure, 4. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days)-Sunshine duration, 5. Mean surface air pressure-Mean Precipitation, 6. Mean Precipitation-Day length, 7. Mean Precipitation-Global radiation, 8. Mean Precipitation-Mean surface air pressure, 9. Mean Precipitation-Sunshine duration, 10. Surface air Pressure-Dewpoint temperature-Mean Precipitation, 11. Relative Humidity-Day length, 12. Relative Humidity-Global radiation, 13. Relative Humidity-Mean surface air pressure, 14. Relative Humidity - Sunshine duration.

Combinations No. 1, 5 and 9 were considered to have a satisfactory fitting.

Figure E-4. Reconstruction of averaged modelled (turquoise) and laboratory-confirmed reported cases (red) conditional to **temperature amplitude** combined with other weather factors, averaged at daily resolution across England and Wales for the years 2000-2016. Modelled cases were calculated according to their conditioning to combination of temperature amplitude and:

1. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Day length,
2. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Global radiation,
3. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Mean surface air pressure,
4. Cumulative Precipitation (7 days) - Sunshine duration,
5. Mean Precipitation - Day length,
6. Mean Precipitation - Global radiation,
7. Mean Precipitation - Mean surface air pressure,
8. Mean Precipitation - Sunshine duration,
9. Relative Humidity - Day length,
10. Relative Humidity - Global radiation,
11. Relative Humidity - Mean surface air pressure,
12. Relative Humidity - Sunshine duration.

Combinations No. 1, 5 and 9 were considered to have a satisfactory fitting.

Figure E-5. Reconstruction of averaged modelled (turquoise) and laboratory-confirmed reported cases (red) conditional to different weather combinations averaged at daily resolution across England and Wales for the years 2000-2016. Modelled cases were calculated according to their conditioning to **wind speed** in different combinations from the best performing weather factors from above:

1. Mean wind speed-Mean Precipitation - Day length,
2. Mean dewpoint temperature- Mean wind speed- Day length,
3. Mean air temperature-Mean wind speed -Mean surface air pressure,
4. Mean dewpoint temperature- Mean Precipitation-Mean wind speed,
5. Mean air temperature- Mean Precipitation- Mean wind speed.

Wind speed is the only factor that displayed a radically different result depending on the order of analysis.

6. Indoor temperature – indoor relative humidity – Day length. The results obtained from the indoor conditions are satisfactory, but not substantially different from their outdoor counterparts.

Figure E-6. Effect of the weather on the risk of contracting salmonellosis per 10 million habitants (Y axis) based on the combined effect of mean air temperature (X axis) and day length. Each quadrant has an equivalent amount of observations. An 11% increase in incidence per °C was calculated based on the difference of the

Figure E-7. Conditional incidence based on the effect of mean air temperature alone.

Figure E-8. Conditional incidence based on the effect of day length alone.

A Fraction of incidence and temperature during the exponential phase at 12-15h (bottom-left)

Figure E-9. Continued on next page.

Figure E-9. Continued on next page.

Figure E-9. Continued on next page.

Figure E-9. Conditional incidence chart. Effect of the weather on the risk of contracting salmonellosis per 100 million habitants (Y axis) based on the combined effect of the different weather factors displayed (X axis). Each chart represents different breaks of the factor indicated in the title, with the coloured bands being a range of the third factor considered. The ribbon indicates the uncertainty around the third weather predictor. Note the lack of a clear pattern of the coloured ribbons masked by the uncertainty.

F. Other time lags explored

Figure F-1. Reconstruction of aggregated salmonellosis cases conditional to the effect of mean air temperature, relative humidity and day length with time lags of 7 (A), 14 (B), 30 (C) and 60 (D) days.

G. Breakdown of the 15 climate change projections for 2043 from all members

Figure G-1. Performance of the conditional incidence model according to each of the global projections (60km) of the 15 MetOffice Hadley Centre climate models or members (HadGEM3-GC3.05) for the year 2043, RCP 8.5.

Figure G-2. Number of instances in a daily basis when a novel climate condition was forecasted for all climate members and all years studied. A similar pattern can be observed for every year. An average of 1500 instances were absent per member per year. For these number of instances, the cases estimated by the model were extrapolated.

